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Islam and Waldorf education -
an exploration of resonance and
ways to facilitate Muslim participation

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Abstract

Although Waldorf education resonates remarkably with Islamic life practice on several levels, the number of children from Muslim families is disproportionately small at Waldorf schools in Germany and the UK. This thesis aims to explore possible causes and collect incentives for addressing the matter in constructive ways. In order to establish how a Muslim approach to Waldorf education can be facilitated, it examines first some of the congruities, then the obstacles, supported by a survey among practising Muslim parents and finally the possibilities, illustrated by examples of trailblazers in Cambridge, Luxor and Los Angeles. Main merits of Waldorf education from a Muslim viewpoint were found in its holistic teaching approach, which takes into account not only children's intellectual and physical development but also their spiritual and artistic unfolding. Several aspects became apparent which, once addressed, can make Waldorf education more accessible for Muslims and thereby respond to the recent resolve for a conscious renewal within the Waldorf movement.

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1 Introduction

When I introduced myself at the Steiner teacher training course in York back in 2019, having brought along a friend who was Muslim like myself, the senior teachers' reply went right to my heart, and set things in motion. Perching on the edge of the chair, they looked us straight in the eye and said: "We've been waiting for you! We have been waiting for people like you to join us and share their perspective with us." I hadn't encountered quite such genuine open-mindedness back in Germany nor in Iceland nearly twenty years earlier, when I first found myself volunteering in various established Waldorf settings as part of an abroad work experience. The interaction that followed in York was deeply inspiring and rewarding, ultimately leading to the discovery that my way of life as a practising Muslim resonates on various levels with the Waldorf educational approach.

Waldorf education, as I have come to know it, is an enormous treasure trove for Muslim parents looking for a counterweight to the characteristics of this time such as materialism, consumerism and meaninglessness leading to nihilism. In spite of that, we see the bulk of Muslim children being processed in mainstream schools, and graduating (or "failing" to) - minus their self esteem, access to their creativity and their love for taking responsibility. I have often been saddened to notice in many of them a hunched posture and evasive expression, much in contrast to what I had seen when I attended a graduation ceremony at a Waldorf school several years previously. It had struck me then how one of the graduates who stood apart by herself, having read her final grade certificate, hugged it to her chest with a radiant smile and an expression that read, very clearly: "You have recognized me, and I thank you! Now, I can't wait to begin my work in the world - my life."

I then had looked around and noticed in the other graduates, too, an *uprightness* in their posture that impressed me, because it seemed to reflect something about their intention. I later learned that intention is considered one of the four dimensions in which one moves when doing eurythmy, a technique aiming to counteract mendacity among other things, by practising to align "*the soul's inner movement and the body's outer movement*" (Karnieli, 2016, 9). That of course is intriguing from a Muslim point of view, since according to our tradition, "*actions are only by intentions*" (Imam an-Nawwawi, 2023, 6), meaning that what will be counted for or against us after this life is our intention in everything we did or didn't do, rather than the actual results. And since none of our obligatory prayers, our fasting or our various purifying rituals are valid unless we have consciously made the according intention, it certainly seems conducive to train this essential capacity.

Having begun with the mention of what many might consider the most peculiar of Waldorf-features, a subject belonging to the arts – eurythmy – I will further address a range of other aspects of Waldorf education that should sound familiar to Muslims. The seven-year-cycles of a child's development are a well-known example, as is the shared understanding that there is an unseen, which is like ourselves part of creation. The most weighty is certainly the perception of our own spiritual dimension as link to the Creative Entity that originates everything - the Divine, which Muslims call by the name of Allah.

What is it then that prevents this considerable demographic group from being more strongly represented in local Waldorf schools? For one thing, it appears that the reservations some Muslim parents have about sending their children to Waldorf settings are founded on a number of misconceptions regarding Steiner's educational philosophy. There are, however, certain matters children will most likely be facing at many present-day Waldorf schools that are indeed problematic if not altogether incompatible with the life transaction called Islam. Identifying both the

misconceptions and the actual issues of (unintentional) exclusion will be attempted in chapter 3 of this thesis, followed by prospects of finding creative and constructive ways of dealing with the latter.

2 Why?

A current estimate states that today there are more than one and a half billion Muslims in the world ([Data Pendas, 2024](#)), inhabiting regions *"from Morocco in the west to Bangladesh in the east, in the steppes of central Asia to the north, and the island world of Indonesia to the south."* (Küng, 1988, cited after [Köylü, 2008](#)). Based on the young age of most Muslims and their high fertility rate, this number is projected to grow increasingly (cf. [Pew Research Center, 2015](#)). The Waldorf movement, too, has expanded globally into India, Kenya, Tanzania, China, Taiwan, the Middle East and altogether more than eighty countries (cf. [Waldorf UK, 2024](#)), which comprise a vast spectrum of diverse cultures and spiritual practices. Conversely, population composition within Europe and the United States - where Waldorf education first took root - has diversified immensely with regards to ethnic, cultural and religious background. Since the first Waldorf school was established, one hundred years have passed and in order to stay true to the original vision of its founder, Rudolf Steiner, the Waldorf movement has recently made efforts to acknowledge this widened diversity of students, and to allow and ensure for it to reflect in the form and contents of the lessons. Based on my own personal background of being Muslim as well as German, in fact Bavarian by origin, it is my hope to contribute to this process by providing some mutual insights to both Waldorf teachers and Muslim parents, whatever their ethnic provenance or cultural background.

2.1. Shared Ambitions

This poetic impression of the essence of Waldorf Education was given to the very first college of teachers by Rudolf Steiner in Stuttgart in 1921:

May there reign here spirit-strength in love;
may there work here spirit-light in goodness;
 born from certainty of heart,
 and from steadfastness of soul,
by which we may nurture in young human beings
 bodily strength for work,
 depth of soul,
 and clarity of spirit.

The time in which this was written shows certain similarities to our present-day. Public opinion was informed by materialism, war was looming and the ruling class characterized by a spiritual void. Today, looking at the education system we find that while cultivating students' physical strength and intellectual capacities may be what many conventional schools aim for, educating the qualities of the soul is not usually regarded as relevant within those settings.

Essential educational aims from a Muslim viewpoint are sound character (Arabic: *akhlaq*) and the capabilities required to do good actions (Arabic: *'amal as-sâlih*). I am going to highlight a few aspects here that are vital to this pursuit and, while mostly alien to state school curricula, they distinctly resonate with the Waldorf educational approach.

2.1.1 Basic self-conception as spiritual beings

From a Muslim point of view, physical existence is a transitional state with a certain purpose. Rather than identifying with only the physical body, Muslims consider the essential entity in each human, called *rūḥ* in Arabic, to be that which remains in

eternity once the body has ceased to live. Babies, suddenly focusing on something and smiling at where we see nothing, are believed to see in that moment angels, recognizing them from *jannah* (paradise), where all the *arwah* (plural of *rūḥ*) are gathered before entering their physical bodies. This understanding of life existing beyond matter is central also to Rudolf Steiner's philosophy which, while clearly distinguishable from Islamic life practice in its entirety, characterises his educational approach accordingly. He declared that a human being's full potential can only unfold if alongside the physical body and the mind, a person's spirituality is developed, too. In Islamic terms, the latter would be called *fitrah* and is defined by Imam al-Ghazali as the innate capacity to recognise God (cf. [Nieto, 2023](#)). Ibn Arabi described it as *"the original and unalterable essence of the human creature that enables him not only to recognise Reality, but to be a mirror of it"* (Nieto, 2023). Another great sufi scholar, Abdul Qadir Al-Jilani, has defined it as *"the primal and natural state of the human being before being altered by external circumstances"* (Nieto, 2023). To preserve and nurture this innate sense of connectedness to the Divine can be counted among the aspirations that Waldorf education and Muslim parents and teachers share.

While the manner in which spirituality and the unseen are sometimes addressed in Waldorf settings does, from a Muslim perspective, contain controversial aspects, the general affirmation of the human being as a creature with spiritual qualities to be cultivated is unequivocally shared by practising Muslims. It also stands quite in contrast to the purely materialistic world view of the state school system. Indeed, several of the basic qualities that Muslims strive to teach their children are also featured in the current syllabus for religious education on Waldorf schools in Germany. A closer look will be provided in chapter 3.2.1.

2.1.2 Purpose and Responsibility

If a child has been able in his play to give up his whole loving being to the world around him, he will be able, in the serious tasks of later life, to devote himself with confidence and power to the service of the world.¹

Muslims consider the limited time in the material world to be the „time of actions“, the opportunity to apply one’s gifts and capabilities to the benefit of those in need, and thereby gain Allah’s pleasure. Once all agency has come to an end along with a person’s physical existence, that is considered to be the „time of meanings“, where the meaning of every previous action will be made clear. As mentioned in the introduction, this refers not to the result of the action but to its intention (Arabic: *niyyah*). Being able to differentiate between doing something intentionally or unconsciously if not automatically, is therefore to be regarded as an essential skill. In view of this, a school curriculum that inherently provides for its training surely accommodates the educational responsibilities of Muslim parents. This aspect may even serve as an incentive for them to contemplate the potential of eurythmy, the subject unique to Waldorf education and known for its quaintness. However, it is also within the framework of the other subjects such as science and crafts like woodworking and copper moulding that “will” in its varying modalities is developed and educated in Waldorf schools (chapters 2.1.4 and 2.1.5). Steiner emphasized the relevance of this aspect, and in his teaching recommendations for each subject, scope is given for the experience and formation of will, suited to the students’ respective developmental stages.

¹A quote attributed to Rudolf Steiner and a frequent motto at Waldorf kindergartens and early years teacher trainings. Most likely from one of the various English-translations of GA307 (1986), known in English-speaking Waldorf schools as the Ilkley Lectures.

The education and teaching of the future will have to set particular value on the development of the will and feeling nature. (...) Feeling and will are left more and more to what is called chance, because there is no insight into the real nature of will. (Steiner, *The Foundations of Human Experience*, Lecture 4)

Having developed his will to a certain degree, it becomes then possible for the young person to consciously apply his gifts and capabilities to the service of creation (Arabic: *khidma*) rather than profit maximization.

Another congenial aspect characteristic for Waldorf education is the sense of connectedness with nature. Looking at the devastating, long term environmental damages caused by only decades of consumerist culture, it becomes poignantly clear that both present and future generations require an unquestioned sense of responsibility towards creation in order to counteract the destructive course that has lead us to this point. This concept of the human being as creation's custodian is mentioned several times in the Qur'an, as well as in the oral tradition of the Prophet Muhammad: *"The world is sweet and green, and verily Allah is going to install you as vicegerents in it in order to see how you act"* (Sahih Muslim, cited after [Azman, 2023](#)). However, there is the disturbing observation that present-day Muslims are not generally fit to serve as examples for upholding environmental responsibility. As Hajj Fazlun Khalid, Founder-Director of the Islamic Foundation for Ecology and Environmental Science (IFEES), points out: *"The textual tradition in Islam is deep and profound but current Muslim practice is shallow as priority is now given to economic drivers."* ([Fazlun Khalid, 2017](#), 3). He has addressed the issue in multiple ways over the last decades, for example in this article in the Encyclopedia of Global Environmental Change:

As what we now understand by modernity advanced, as the secular ethic progressively seeped into the Muslim psyche and as industrial development, economic indicators and consumerism became the govern-

ing parameters of society, there has been a corresponding erosion of the Muslim perception of the holistic and a withering of its understanding of the sacred nexus between the human community and the rest of the natural order: *"The creation of the heavens and the earth is far greater than the creation of mankind. But most of mankind do not know it"* (Qur'an 40:56). ([Khalid, 2002](#), 3)

Considering this, a learning environment where cultivating children's connectedness with nature is inherently part of the daily routine throughout primary school, and on a different level throughout middle and upper school as well, may be appreciated as an opportunity to be cherished by Muslim parents. For, as David Attenborough has pointed out, *"No one will protect what they don't care about and no one will care about what they haven't experienced."* (Attenborough, 1995 quoted after [Palmer, 2018](#), 16).

In order for the students to establish a conscious relationship with nature, Waldorf teaching implements Goethean science (see 2.1.3) in various subjects such as arts and nature studies. Prior to this, during the first seven years in particular, great emphasis is placed on preserving and maintaining the small child's innate sense of connectedness with nature. This reflects manifold in the materials and activities children are typically exposed to during this developmental phase. For example, rather than giving any pre-defined (often plastic) toys to the small child, she is left to play with smooth bits of wood, patterned pebbles, „play-silk“ or other unicoloured fabrics, and whatever else she herself may discover outdoors. These transform momentarily into whatever is required for the child's imagined play, and while she familiarises herself with the materials and processes of the natural world, this approach also allows for her creative and imaginative thinking to unfold and develop freely (cf. O'Brien, Liz et al. 2011; [Dadvand, Payam et.al. 2015](#)).

2.1.3 Holistic pursuit of knowledge

The heart of the Waldorf method is that education is an art - it must speak to the child's experience. To educate the whole child, his heart and his will must be reached, as well as the mind.²

For Muslim parents and teachers, educational aims of significant importance are awareness with regards to our purpose in creation, and agency on both an intellectual and a physical level in order to fulfil this purpose as best one can - in the seen and unseen. In Waldorf terms, education must always refer to "Head, Heart and Hands", so that the intellect as well as the character and the physical or artistic capabilities of a student can unfold their full potential. To this end, Waldorf teaching endeavours to enable students' development and integration of *thinking, feeling and willing* – which ultimately is what makes it an art.

Art moves the person in non-intellectual ways and has an effect primarily on the feeling life and activates the will. An artistic way of teaching means composing the whole in a way that engages the whole human being and is a response to the actual situation. It is aesthetic in that it imbues what we do with meaning and edifies us. ([Rawson, 2017](#), 3)

One of the techniques applied in this art is referred to as phenomenology, an approach to science based on which sensory impressions are, inevitably, the starting point for all empirical knowledge (cf. [D'Aleo, 2003](#)). With regards to the young child, education consists less in teaching than in providing an adequate environment that

²A quote accredited to Rudolf Steiner, found on the websites of many English-language Waldorf Schools such as [Tamarack Waldorf School](#) and [Eugene Waldorf School](#) . Most likely from one of the various English-translations of GA 307 (1986), known in English-speaking Waldorf schools as the Ilkley Lectures.

offers rich sensations and deep context, such as nature itself (cf. [D'Aleo, 2003](#)). By contrast, in terms of middle and upper school students which are already able to distinguish between their actual sensory perceptions such as smells and sounds, and their thoughts and feelings evoked by those perceptions, phenomenology is specifically applied as a teaching method, mainly in science class:

In a phenomenological approach, one strives to give the students an experience of the phenomena and then have them wrestle with finding relationships or order. This process actually cultivates the true powers and capacities necessary for thinking. Here thinking becomes an activity, a verb, something that is dynamic and living. ([D'Aleo, 2003](#), 3)

A story from the Qur'an illustrates this very capacity to think actively and dynamically. It is a narration from the life of the Prophet Ibrāhīm (Abraham) that occurred when he was not yet an adult and growing up amongst a people whose established religious practice it was to pray and sacrifice to statues. Following his longing to know the origin of all power, he sets out to undertake some independent observations. Surah 6 (al-An'aam/The Cattle) tells about how one night, Ibrāhīm gazes at a star. He is filled with a sense of awe and wonder and the impulse to worship it. However, as the night passes the star sets, and Ibrāhīm feels disillusioned. He then observes the moon, and again is overcome with awe and wonder, considering the moon to be his "Lord". When it too, sets, he becomes aware of the fallibility of his own cognition: *"If my Lord does not guide me, I will be one of the misguided people."* (surah 6/The Cattle, aayat 77). As the sun rises, he realizes it is far greater and more radiant than the moon: *"This is my Lord! This is greater!"* (surah 6/The Cattle, aayat 78). It is not difficult to imagine the magnificence of the moment when, at the end of the day, the sun does set as well, and Ibrāhīm arrives at his final conclusion that no transient, created thing or being is worth worshipping - but rather the Power itself that creates them:

'My people, I am free of what you associate with Allah! I have turned my face to Him Who brought the heavens and earth into being, (as) a pure natural believer. I am not one of the idolators.' (surah 6/The Cattle, aayats 78-79)

Ibrāhīm then challenges the practices of his community including his father:

Recite to them the story of Ibrāhīm when he said to his father and his people, 'What do you worship?' They said, 'We worship idols and will continue to cling to them.' He said, 'Do they hear you when you call or do they help you or do you harm?' They said, 'No, but this is what we found our fathers doing.' He said, 'Have you really thought about what you worship, you and your fathers who came before?' (surah 26/The Poets, aayats 69 – 76)

His appeal to them to reflect on the validity of their customary acts of worship is met with a rebuff, and so he contrives a way of demonstrating to them the futility of worshipping created things such as statues. The Qur'an recounts what might be called a prank, as follows:

He broke them in pieces, except for the biggest one, so that they would have it to consult! They said, 'Who has done this to our gods? He is definitely one of the wrongdoers!' They said, 'We heard a young man mentioning them. They call him Ibrāhīm.' They said, 'Bring him before the people's eyes so they can be witnesses.' They asked, 'Did you do this to our gods, Ibrāhīm?' He said, 'No, this one, the biggest of them, did it. Ask them if they are able to speak!' (surah 21/The Prophets, aayats 58 - 63)

After consulting among themselves, they come to recognize the erroneousness of their established practice. However, soon they lapse back into their habits, and when asked about it by Ibrāhīm, they dismiss his argument. He resolutely adheres to his finding and calls on them to use their intellect – which leads to a fierce response:

(They said), 'You know full well these idols cannot talk.' He said, 'Do you then worship, instead of Allah, what cannot help or harm you in any way? Shame on you and what you worship besides Allah! Will you not use your intellect?' They said, 'Burn him and support your gods if you are resolved to do something.' We said, 'Fire, be coolness and peace for Ibrāhīm!' (surah 21/The Prophets, aayats 65 - 69)

Ibrāhīm is indeed known as the prophet for whom Allah has made fire cool and soothing when he was thrown into it by his own people, so he came out of it unharmed. This story also illustrates how free thinking can have a profound impact on society, and how due to that, it carries a risk of punishment for rejecting societal norms.

Steiner's aim, "*Education towards Freedom*" (Carlgren, 2009) of which the development of free thinking is one aspect, will be looked at further in chapter 2.1.5. With regards to a holistic pursuit of knowledge as in perceiving and comprehending phenomena on more than just a cognitive level, I would like to introduce the Islamic term '*Aql*' here in order to illustrate another example of consonance with the Waldorf educational approach. '*Aql*' translates from Arabic as cognition or "*sense, sentience, reason, understanding, comprehension, discernment, insight, rationality, mind, intellect, intelligence*" (Hans Wehr, 1979, 737). While "intellect" is the most commonly used translation, '*Aql*' does imply more than a faculty that deals with propositions by means of logic. The Qur'an mentions that it is an activity of the heart:

Have they not travelled about the earth and do they not have **hearts to understand with** or ears to hear with? It is not eyes that are blind but hearts in breasts that are blind. (surah 22/al-Hajj, aayat 46) [my emphasis]

The heart is identified as a sense organ in the Qur'an:

It is He who has created **hearing, sight and hearts** for you. What little thanks you show! It is He who dispersed you about the earth and you will be gathered to Him. It is He who gives life and causes to die and His is the alternation of night and day. So will you not **use your intellect?** (surah 23/ The Believers, aayats 78 – 80) [my emphasis]

Accordingly, 'Aql denotes agency to perceive, discern and comprehend, and is located in our heart. Any islamically motivated educational endeavour may be assumed to welcome teaching methods that nurture this faculty.

Steiner came to explore and expand on phenomenology in the course of his work as editor of Goethe's scientific writings. His introductions to Goethe's texts "*establish the epistemological basis for a science that reveals the essential, spiritual nature of the sense-perceptible world.*" (Steiner & Barnes, 2000, 1). Goethe in his activity as a researcher of nature had practised and developed a "*participatory, morally-responsive, and holistic approach to the description of dynamic life-world phenomena*" ([Robbins, 2006](#), 1):

Goetheanism assumes that (...) one can experience the orderly content of the real external world and that genuine object cognition is possible. The decisive thing is to reach the object in its inherent lawfulness in cognition ['Aql, A/N] and to form concepts from it - and not only to find what the mind puts into it. (Rosslénbroich, 2022, cited after [Akanthos Akademie, 2023](#))

This capacity of genuine object cognition is indeed possible according to the Qur'an, where Muslims are repeatedly reminded and urged to make use of it in order to grasp the meanings of creation. A selection of verses (Arabic: *ayat*) may serve as an illustration:

Among His Signs is that He shows you lightning, a source of fear and eager hope, and sends down water from the sky, bringing the dead earth back to life by it. There are certainly Signs in that for people who use their intellect. (surah 30/The Romans, aayat 24)

When We grant long life to people, We return them to their primal state. So will you not use your intellect? (surah 36/Ya Sin, aayat 68)

And from the fruit of the date-palm and the grape-vine you derive both intoxicants and wholesome provision. There is certainly a Sign in that for people who use their intellect. (surah 16/The Bee, aayat 67)

In the earth there are diverse regions side by side and gardens of grapes and cultivated fields, and palm-trees sharing one root and others with individual roots, all watered with the same water. And We make some things better to eat than others. There are Signs in that for people who use their intellect. (surah 13/Thunder, aayat 4)

Know that Allah brings the earth to life after it was dead. We have made the Signs clear to you so that hopefully you will use your intellect. (surah 57/Iron, aayat 17)

These *aayats* also exemplify the frequent use of metaphor and allegory (Arabic: *mithal*) in the Qur'an. Metaphoric wisdom is recognized as a prophetic teaching method (cf. Asvat, 2015, 61 f) and activator of the human heart. They enable transmission of knowledge on more than just a cognitive level and therefore play an important role both in Islam and in Waldorf teaching. They also relate to another distinctive teaching method recommended by Steiner especially for the lower and middle school, referred to as image-based or imaginal teaching (cf. [Wiehl, 2016](#), 31):

Für die Waldorfpädagogik sieht Steiner vor, dass sie nicht nur auf die sinnliche Wahrnehmung durch das Präsentieren von Gegenständen oder Abbildungen zurückgreift, sondern dass vielmehr die innere Anschaulich-

keit durch lebendige Lehrerzählungen und einen bildhaften, künstlerischen Unterricht gepflegt werden. ([Wiehl, 2016](#), 35)

Steiner envisaged for Waldorf education not to resort only to sensory perception by means of presenting objects or pictures, but rather to cultivate inner vividness through teachers' lively narrations and an imaginal, artistic teaching style. [KG translation]

When introducing students for example to a historical event or a natural phenomenon, simply showing them pictures as a representation of it would be suboptimal, Wiehl explains. Instead, teachers should endeavour to bring the event or phenomenon to mind for the students by accurately transmitting the content verbally or even facilitating a direct experience where possible. In this way, the internal process of forming a vivid, imagined picture can happen more actively and on a more personal level ([Wiehl, 2016](#), 38). Internal and external pictures each have a different impact on the learning process: while showing students a picture does involve their senses more than exposing them to plain information, acquisition of a knowledge that is individually relevant can in fact only take place by students themselves actively generating an internal image of the object of learning ([Wiehl, 2016](#), 32). Although using vibrant chalkboard drawings to create a certain mood conducive to the subject is common practice amongst Waldorf primary school teachers, it is intended to be of secondary importance compared to skilful storytelling. This is because an image, when represented in form of a picture or artefact, pauses. In active language however, the image continues to unfold (cf. [Gläser, 2022](#)). Wiehl therefore compares pictorial narration to a movement of internal images, similar to dreams. Generated by the child's own imagination, internal images do not come to a halt. They are potent, as they affect him not only intellectually, but also in the realm of emotions and will - without overpowering him. As his comprehension and discernment grow, his internal images continue to develop accordingly (cf. [Gläser,](#)

2022). Steiner suggests to end each lesson by gifting the students with internal images such as a story or a poem, that continue in their memory and serve to consolidate what they have learned (cf. [Wiehl, 2016](#), 37).

So as to ensure that not only the intellect but all the senses are cultivated and trained, Waldorf teachers use language to inspire students to develop vivid internal images of phenomena, events, persons or objects. Wiehl mentions an interesting differentiation at this point: it is not the described sensory object as such that provides insights, but rather it constitutes the cause for sensory experiences to emerge, which then may lead to insights. She further illustrates that training this capacity to form internal images also serves as a counterweight to the dominance of external, visual images in contemporary culture. Being familiar with handling one's own internal images consciously and actively implies the development of autonomy and ultimately media competence (cf. [Wiehl, 2016](#), 39).

2.1.4 Refinement of character

While the above chapter gives some examples of the ways in which Waldorf education aspires to support the unfolding of children's intellectual agency, the following introduces some of its aspects that are relevant to the development of their character.

With regards to lower and middle school in particular, Steiner brought into use the four temperament theory as a tool for teachers to reflect on and work with their own dispositions and, based on that, respond to the different children justly and empathetically (cf. Lonnemann und v. Pfulstein, [2023](#)). Knowing and holding the reins of their own emotions or "*soul forces*" ([Riethmüller, 2005](#), 11), teachers can serve as an example which, in the Muslim tradition, is considered the ultimate form of teaching as embodied by the Prophet Muhammad. This degree of autonomy over their

own mood tendencies, if established, also enables teachers to encounter children's varying dispositions with kindness and curiosity instead of demanding obedient uniformity (cf. Lonnemann und v. Pfuhlstein, [2023](#)). In cultivating an understanding of children's emotional constitutions and individual capacities, teachers are then able to consider these in their teaching style:

(...) the teacher will find helpful pointers for the pedagogical methods to be applied in school: she will need to alternate between different modes and know when to bring in variety and stimulus, evenness and quiet, concentrated activity or impressive thoughtfulness. In so doing, one is in line with the different soul moods of the children and not one's own. (...) This is the tenor of Steiner's recommendations— which are not prescriptions! For child observation and reflection on the many impressions received, it can also be helpful to take into account the qualities of "fire, air, water, and earth." ([Riethmüller, 11](#))

In developing this approach, Steiner drew on the four-humour-model of Greek physician Hippocrates, which during the 9th and 10th century had been applied and expanded by Ibn Sina (Avicenna) and other Muslim physicians into the Unani system of medicine, a comprehensive, holistic medical system ([Ahmad&Akhtar 2007](#), 210). Unani looks at the human body as a single unit made of seven components, amongst them the temperaments (Arabic: *mizaj*). Steiner considers the temperaments as one of several personality aspects that require special care and attention during lower and middle school years, the others being disposition, talent, memory, character, habits and forces of the intellect (cf. Riethmüller, [2005](#), 12). While no child embodies only one temperament but always a melange of all four, there is usually one that is dominant. The teacher's task is to help each child move towards his balance (Arabic: *mizan*) while acknowledging and appreciating his temperament:

According to Steiner, one should take into account what is there and recognize the positive qualities of a particular temperament. Such a method is far more fruitful than taking measures to awaken something

which is not present in the child, for example, by attempting to counter a melancholy disposition by exaggerated outward cheerfulness. This principle, by the way, the practice of starting from the talents, gifts, and dispositions which the child actually has, is a basic principle of the Waldorf school, and it is applied from early childhood on. ([Riethmüller, 2005](#), 11)

This, however, does not suggest teachers should generally take the soft option or prompt their students to do so. Quite the contrary, the children get to experience a variety of challenging endeavours suited to their developmental stages, specifically chosen to develop and educate their will along with their feeling and their thinking (cf. Howard, 2002/2, 1). To this end, the Waldorf handwork and crafts curriculum of the lower school comprises knitting, crocheting, felting and working with other textiles as well as woodwork. In middle school, dressmaking, basket-weaving, copper-beating and forging iron are added; spinning, weaving, bookbinding and smelting are further activities for the upper school students. Each craft, when practised, impacts certain areas of development in the child or young adult's character, as copious sources outside the scale of this thesis will illustrate (e.g. [Graves, 2011](#)). While will as the "*inner force behind the outer force of our limbs*" ([Howard, 2002/1](#), 1) is exercised every time we are challenged to make an inner effort, it does not conclude that the strength of will is always reflected in the result of the effort made:

We must allow for a certain law of inner development: the time it takes for effort of will to bear fruit in outer results is outside human control - that of the individual, parents, teachers. We must make the effort, but the results are in God's time. ([Howard, 2002/1](#), 2)

This principle resonates also with the Waldorf convention that children's efforts are not judged by means of grades until upper school. Drastically different from state schools where students routinely resort to cramming with no interest or intention to retain what they have learned, in Waldorf education the point of acquiring new skills

or knowledge is to increase the young person's range of possibilities to apply and make good use of their will in the world. Wolfgang-M. Auer uses the picture of a stream of water to illustrate how will develops in individual human beings:

Whenever we learn a movement, activity, technique or a new language, a new channel is made or an existing one widened or deepened. Then the intentions, or will impulses, can stream through the body and our newly acquired skills can get out into the world and take effect there. ([Auer, 2023](#))

In thus fortifying his will and confidence to take on responsibility in life, a young person's character is given scope to refine in ways that would be largely inaccessible at regular schools. It is further conducive to the development of his awareness and agency that Waldorf handwork and crafts lessons mostly include a first introduction to aspects of production and commerce and the global as well as ecological implications. Taking into consideration the artistic, creative dimension of the subject, Beaven and McDermott highlight its relevance by pointing out that an over-emphasis on sciences, career-readiness, business and technology compromises the development of full, human potential unless the arts in their various forms receive equal focus, providing opportunities for creative expression and exploration of the "*deep dimensions of human experience*" ([Beaven & McDermott, 2021](#), 10). Since examining the great variety of subjects in a Waldorf curriculum with regards to their specific impact on the development of students' character is not the topic of this thesis, I would instead like to point those further interested towards the references at the end and insert here this exemplary illustration of the rhizomic (cf. Boland & Rawson, 2023, 2) curriculum pattern for a North European Waldorf school just by way of providing an idea of its comprehensiveness:

[Waldorf curriculum chart]. Gaia Waldorf School. URL (<https://www.gaiawaldorf.co.za/our-curriculum/>)

So by attributing equal weight and consideration in the curriculum to the arts and crafts in comparison to maths, science and languages, opportunities are provided for students to develop their feeling will through the experience of creating something with their own hands. Besides serving as “a healthy antidote to becoming passive consumers” (Howard, 2002/2, 4), this is an essential process also in view of the contributions the young person may later actively bring to society:

As our feeling will awakens through activities such as the arts and crafts, it will become active in other domains such as social life. We will feel more intensely the rigidity and clumsiness of social forms. Our feeling will awakens our creative will to be social sculptors who transform dead and chaotic social forms into more living and harmonious ones. (Howard, 2002/2, 5)

2.1.5 *Education to freedom*

Our highest endeavor must be to develop free human beings who are able of themselves to impart purpose and direction to their lives. The need for imagination, a sense of truth, and a feeling of responsibility—these three forces are the very nerve of education. ([Marie Steiner, 1923](#))

In his endeavour to design an *“Education to freedom”* (Carlgren, 2009), Rudolf Steiner envisaged an educational approach that strives to clear out as many physical and psychological obstacles as possible, which might otherwise obstruct an individual’s freedom to take action in adult life. The greater the range of means of expression accessible to the individual and the more consciously he is able to apply them, unhampered in his thinking and decision making by inner or outer distractions, the higher, according to Steiner, is his level of inner freedom (cf. v. Schwanenflügel, 2022). Without this inner freedom, *“our outer freedom is largely an illusion that works against our well-being”* (Howard, 2002/1, 4). At the time in Germany between the two world wars, Steiner warned of future political activity aiming to set people into stereotypes so they can be pulled about as if by wires, all the while imagining that they are greatly progressive and, free (cf. Steiner, 2019, 31). One century later, we find ourselves and our digital data considered as commodities by the prevalent economic system, and our freedom reduced to mere compliance (cf. [Zuboff, 2023](#)). Facilitating students’ development of free will is therefore vital more than ever also from a Muslim viewpoint, and it was Steiner’s ambition with regards to the curriculum for each of the subjects.

The question should not be: What does a human being need to know and be able to do for the social order that now exists?, but rather: What capacities are latent in this human being, and what lies within that can be developed? (...) The rising generation should not be molded into what the existing social order chooses to make of it. (Steiner, 1985, 71, quoted after [Bransby and Rawson, 2020](#))

2.2 Speaking of inclusion

If we are able to see why Waldorf education presents indeed an interesting option for Muslim parents, we may now take a closer look at why it should be in the interests of the Waldorf community to undertake deeper reflections on its accessibility concerning Muslims. Besides the curiosity that is characteristic for most Waldorf teachers, another incentive would be the aspiration to become a truly socially inclusive school, and the contribution this would mean towards improving overall social discourse. The latter is expressed in this excerpt from a listing of Waldorf pedagogy core aims:

- Support and enable children and young people to become socially capable and responsible members of their communities and be able to contribute constructively to the society they are embedded in and also to be capable of living and working peacefully, respectfully and fruitfully with people of different personal, social and cultural backgrounds.
- Support and enable young people to develop the powers of critical judgement, narrative empathy (the ability to tell the story of the Other) and cosmopolitan or global citizenship.
- Support and enable young people to construct robust and durable identities. (Rawson, 2017, 5)

Considering that the point of inclusivity is to enable all children to develop a sense of dignity, self worth and belonging (cf. Schmelzer 2021), its pursuit serves the third of the above aims in particular. Waldorf education presents a special potential for inclusivity on various levels, which, however, is a topic this thesis does not attempt not cover. The following chapters aim to highlight the aspect of inclusivity with regards to diverse spiritual practices, as I suggest calling it. That is in order to distinguish the sensitivities of (according to their abilities) practising Muslims from those who carry this label as a form of birthmark, some more and some less proudly, but

without feeling intrinsically bound to the actual life practice of Islam. While a differentiation is occasionally made between cultural and religious diversity, both of which are to be acknowledged as enriching elements in the process of identity formation (cf. Schmelzer, 2021), the term “religiousness” is historically charged and does not necessarily impart the meaning of a conscious, spiritual life practice.

2.2.1 *Original Aspirations*

The founding history shows that in conceptualizing the Waldorf educational approach, Rudolf Steiner envisaged for all children, regardless of socio-economic background, capability or any other applicable category, to receive education in a holistic sense, equipping them “*for the needs of the time and under the given social conditions*” ([Barth & Wiehl, 2024](#), 3). The first Waldorf school was established in the period of upheaval after World War I, in 1919 in the south of Germany in Stuttgart. In view of the disillusionment amongst his workers regarding the social system and its political leaders, Emil Molt, owner of the Waldorf-Astoria cigarette factory, sought to provide education for his employees’ children that would truly improve their prospects. He commissioned Steiner with this task, and his efforts were well received:

(...) the workers were captivated by the imagination and vision of a radical, new form of education in which the children of workers and management would be educated together throughout a full twelve grades (ages 6–18). (Ashley, 2009, 210)

As observed by Martyn Rawson in his recent work on decolonizing the Waldorf curriculum, Steiner’s vision could not be fully implemented even in the first Waldorf school in Stuttgart, where classes ultimately consisted of a majority of children from the educated middle class and children of anthroposophists (cf. [Rawson](#),

[2023](#), 15). However, Steiner's conditions for his school were that girls, too, must be admitted and that teachers must be autonomous in their teaching rather than answerable to state standards, so that lessons could be developed based on students' requirements. Also, there was to be no tuition fee. The aim was for the next generation to unfold their potential as human beings and as better leaders, and to counterbalance the devastation and nihilism prevalent in society at this time (cf. [Antioch University, 2019](#)).

In their article on inclusive Waldorf schools of the 21st century, Ulrike Barth and Angelika Wiehl cite Steiner further on this point: "*What the practice of contemporary life demands of people, it must be reflected in the facilities of this school.*" (Steiner 1919, cited after [Barth & Wiehl, 2024](#)). The authors point out the necessity for every Waldorf school to reconceptualize this principle "*for every social community, culture and language, in accordance with the given conditions.*" ([Barth and Wiehl, 2024](#), 3). Research regarding the latter has made clear that within the German school system in general, children and young people from low-income families with migration history are faced with structural disadvantage (Schmelzer, 2021, 2; [BdFW, 2022](#)). At German Waldorf schools, too, they are still underrepresented which, if condoned by teachers, bears the risk of "*imparting a perception of cultural homogeneity to the children that does not align with the reality of our diverse society*" ([Barth & Wiehl, 2024](#), 6). Accordingly, efforts have been made within the Waldorf community to take appropriate action, and intercultural schools were successfully founded in Mannheim, Berlin, Hamburg, Dortmund and Dresden (Schmelzer, 2021, 3). The research center of the Federation of German Waldorf Schools (Bund der Freien Waldorfschulen) has published a comprehensive brochure titled "*Steiner/Waldorf Education in a Migration Society*", acknowledging the vast heterogeneity of present day students in terms of their "*social, linguistic, cultural and religious backgrounds*" as a notable challenge for teachers ([BdFW, 2022](#)).

However, these initiatives have also led to the valid question whether "*the founding of schools with an intercultural profile, rather than making it possible for all Waldorf schools to be intercultural*" is in the long run conducive to rising to that challenge ([Rawson, 2023](#), 9).

2.2.2 *Embracing the Challenge*

What struck me as I read through an extensive amount of relevant surveys and articles was that wherever mention is made of Muslims, by default this refers to people with migration history. In these cases, all the considerations expressed in the above-mentioned papers and initiatives of course apply and require cultivation. Apparently though, the idea of Muslims whose culture is not that of a different country, but the local one – however eclectic – does not even occur. This is problematic not only in view of the endeavour to facilitate a settling-in of Islamic life practice into German culture (as opposed to the other way round, cf. [Hernández, 2016](#)), allowing the Muslims who live there to see themselves as part of society as a whole and to feel accepted as such. Considering that Islamic life practice has settled in, shaped and enriched numerous cultures as diverse as those of West Africa, Indonesia, Bosnia and Crimea, for example, it is rather remarkable that this has not as yet happened to a similar extent in Germany. Nevertheless, there is a considerable number of German Muslims with no migration history after 1950, for whom contemporary German culture poses no barrier whatsoever as long as it does not interfere with the requirements of their spiritual practice. It is not only, but especially with regards to this growing group that it can be considered problematic when the distinction between cultural differences and those based on differing spiritual life practices is not made. From a Muslim point of view culture is not specific to belief nor to spiritual practice, but can naturally encompass a variety of those. The Ottoman Empire and al-Andalus, to name but two of the great Islamic

empires, offer an abundance of illuminating examples for wholesome management of “religious pluralism” (cf. [Çevik, 2024](#), 598).

Cultural differences, with regards to a school class of diverse backgrounds, do not pose the same sort of challenge to the teacher as do differences in spiritual practice. While embracing certain elements of a fellow student’s culture can and should be encouraged by teachers, it is a different matter altogether when it comes to affirmations and rituals that are part of a spiritual practice other than the students’ own. Expecting of them to participate when their own spiritual tradition doesn’t allow it, puts them in a quandary they shouldn’t have to face. In the case of children who haven’t reached the age where a commitment to a spiritual practice can be made, it is still crucial how their teacher responds to the sensitivities arising from their family’s spiritual tradition. In disregarding or disparaging the family’s way of life, teachers inadvertently affect the child’s developing self-perception in a way contrary to the fundamental ethos of Steiner Waldorf Education (cf. [Rawson, 2023](#), 12). So how can this challenge, once recognised, be met? The question is examined more closely in chapter 3, along with a brief account of some trailblazers for taking on the task. By way of general advice, Martyn Rawson suggests in his guidelines for developing a global Waldorf curriculum locally that teachers assess their practice based on generic preconditions for learning and development, such as “*the need all people have, to be seen, heard, recognized and accepted*” ([Rawson, 2017](#), 5). With regards to the unhampered development of children’s spirituality in particular, Carlo Willmann observes that the task of ensuring this should already be addressed during teacher training, bearing in mind that it is indeed “*within the purview of Waldorf education*” ([Willmann, 2021](#)). In order to live up to this demand, he proposes, among others, the following question to those concerned with the study of Waldorf education:

How can teachers learn to create an open atmosphere in which the pupils' religious sense and ethical sensibilities are addressed in a way that they can recognize themselves without feeling patronized? ([Willmann, 2021](#))

Willmann has researched this question extensively in his work, some of which is introduced in chapter 3.2.

3 How?

My purpose in suggesting to consider how Waldorf education can be made more accessible for children and young people coming from practising Muslim families, was further strengthened by my personal experience during teacher training. I found that in the context of our courses, while inclusion and sensitivity towards diversity regarding cultural background, gender and sexuality received great emphasis, the Muslim perspective – also on these matters – was altogether lacking. Thankfully, staff at our teacher training seminar excelled, in my view, with regards to accessibility, goodwill and appreciation which allowed me to feel safe enough to express what I had perceived. In making room for my perspective, they also exemplified how we as future teachers are to respond to a diverse body of students. Another takeaway for me in this context was the observation made by my fellow students that indeed, they did not feel equipped to include Muslim sensitivities in their considerations for lesson planning because they simply did not know enough about it. The reasons for this gap in today's western European common knowledge when it comes to Islam as a life practice (rather than a category) present a separate topic of research, perhaps in the context of a Waldorf version of post-colonial studies (cf. [Rawson, 2017](#), 17). The aim of this chapter, however, is to discuss what aspects may be preventing Muslim parents in Germany and England from opting for Waldorf education.

3.1 Identifying the obstacles

Drawing on the insights gained during teacher training and previous encounters with Waldorf education in different settings in Iceland, England and Germany, I found several of its elements to be potentially at odds with the Islamic way of life. However, the more deeply I studied the subject, the more obvious it became to me that some of these elements were not necessarily an integral part of Waldorf education as such, but rather of its underlying theoretical and spiritual framework, Anthroposophy. This refers to the quasi-Christian aspects that typically shape much of the lower grade lesson planning when it comes to storytelling and celebrations, as well as to the idea of reincarnation, implied by many Waldorf teachers in their observations when acknowledging the unfathomable aspects of the individual child and her inherent destiny. However, Anthroposophy is not approved as teaching content, as Steiner clearly stated:

You must realize that the Waldorf School or any other school which might spring from the anthroposophical movement, would never wish to teach its pupils anthroposophy in the form in which it exists today. This I should consider the very worst thing one could do. For anthroposophy in its present form is a subject for grownups and, as one can see from the color of their hair, often for quite mature adults! Consequently it is presented through its literature or by word of mouth in a form appropriate only to the adult. I should consider any passing on to pupils of content taken from my "Theosophy" or from my book "Knowledge of the Higher Worlds and Its Attainment" as the very worst misuse possible ... Anthroposophy itself is not to be taught in a Waldorf School. (Steiner, 1922)

When talking to Muslim parents about Waldorf education during the last ten years, both in the UK and in Germany, most seemed vaguely interested but had not previously heard of Waldorf education. For those who had, I recall their most frequent associations being "outdoor play" and "Christian/esoteric". Of those that were

more familiar with the concept, some remarked that Waldorf was great for small children, but no longer once they reached middle and upper school. This was due to the impression - which some had gained by personal experience - that Waldorf meant prioritizing a playful, creative approach to learning over intellectually demanding tasks (the incompatibility of the two seemed to be implied). Some few others responded with the same enthusiasm that I felt, and for very similar reasons (see chapter 2.1).

In order to find out more about their thoughts on the subject for the purpose of this thesis, I compiled five open questions addressed to practising Muslims into a semi-structured questionnaire, the answers to which I'll aim to summarize here. Additionally, I will refer to the results of a recent workshop on the topic, in which Waldorf parents of various cultural and spiritual background, Waldorf teachers and Waldorf upper school students participated (chapter 3.1.2). Based on that and some theoretical foundations as outlined in chapter 2, I deducted four categories: aspects about Waldorf education that were considered A, appealing or B, unappealing by practising Muslim parents; C, aspects they consider problematic with regards to their Islamic life practice and D, their wishes regarding a Waldorf school that is suitable for their children or grandchildren.

The questionnaire was sent to eight German and eleven English men and women, Muslims of diverse ethnic background, asking them to share with me their thoughts on Waldorf education. Twelve of them felt they knew too little about the subject to be able to answer. Only three of the seven remaining participants have had some previous experience with Waldorf schools. Due to that, the range of elements they may perceive as problematic is not comprehensively reflected in the survey. However, since its purpose was not to supply a theoretical framework, but rather to substantiate and complement the observations made during and previous to my studies, it still serves as a basis for further discussion.

The next chapter examines some of the aspects participants perceived as unappealing or problematic, and relates them to the Waldorf educational approach as envisaged by Rudolf Steiner. An account of experiences made by Muslim Waldorf school students in Germany may serve to deduct further obstacles in chapter 3.1.2. Finally, I will attempt to outline some ways of moving forward in chapter 3.2, based on the remaining two categories, the “appealing aspects” and the wishes Muslim parents have with regards to Waldorf schools suitable for their children.

3.1.1 Misgivings

Of the participants in my survey, those with first-hand experience as Waldorf parents had a multitude of merits to report, and with marked enthusiasm. The relevant excerpts are rendered in the appendix, in order to enable a balanced impression. Here is a summary of the concerns they expressed, which are mostly based on their observations and accordingly limited to the settings they visited. Some, however, stem from the general sense of an implicit, defensive stance against Islam within today’s western culture, and refer to its conceivable impact on the spiritual development of their children. While the purpose of this chapter is mainly to point out to Waldorf teachers some sensitive issues to bear in mind in their encounter with Muslim families, I have also inserted some of Rudolf Steiner’s statements by way of indicating to any concerned, Muslim readers that which may be assumed of teachers’ endeavours and aspirations.

Western view of Islam

One participant worried that the “western view” of Islam he had noted in other educational contexts would also reflect in Waldorf schools, in the form of prejudices about Islam and accordingly negative connotations, to which he would not

want to expose his children (P3). Another participant and Waldorf-parent recounted how Islam had been gravely misrepresented in some classes due to teachers' lack of knowledge, and proposed interfaith teacher training (P5).

A main concern expressed by a participant (P1) was that her small son might attract negative attention if he was to try and do his prayer, or when using Islamic (Arabic) terms as part of his common word usage. If asked "why are you saying such strange things?" rather than "what does that mean?" he might well, in order to fit in, hide his developing Islamic practices and thus be thwarted (P1). This concern is not unfounded, also with regards to older children. A recent publication of the German Federal Agency for Civic Education, examining the topic of "preventing Islamism" from a power-critical perspective, concludes that even just the fear of being labelled negatively can lead young people to avoid any behaviour that is marked as different ([Le et al., 2023](#)).

P1 also worried that Muslim students may be expected to go low in the face of depreciating treatment, and couldn't count on the same level of support as those belonging to other faith-based groups, as had been her previous experience in state school settings.

In his lectures on body, soul and spirit in Waldorf education, Steiner stated:

The teacher is called upon to carry into his lessons the utmost respect for soul and spirit. Without it, he will succeed as little as if he were lacking an even fundamental artistic and scientific background. Therefore the first prerequisite of a Waldorf teacher is to have reverence for the soul and spiritual potential which each child brings with it into the world. (...) When confronted with the child, the teacher must be imbued with the awareness that he is dealing with an innately free human being. With this attitude he will be able to work out educational principles and methods which will safeguard the child's inborn freedom so that in later life, when a pupil looks back upon his school days, he will not find any infringement upon his personal freedom, not even in the aftereffects of his education. (Steiner, 1922, 206)

Christian indoctrination?

Another participant observed that Christian religion was the single denominational religion class offered at the Waldorf school her child visits, which she called “rather regrettable” and even “dramatic”. She believes this to be a disqualifier for many who would otherwise send their children to a Waldorf school, but fear they may be Christianly indoctrinated (P5). On a more general level, one parent whose children had previously visited a Waldorf kindergarten wrote that he disliked the “somewhat cult-like demeanour of some teachers, disabling any questioning of positions” (P4).

Lack of Islamic teaching

The lack of Islamic teaching contents was considered a deficit by several of the participants, one of which suggested the curriculum (in Germany) was outdated in view of a multicultural society (P5). Arabic language, Islamic history, Islamic sciences and arts were suggested as supplementary subjects or as lesson contents (P1, P3, P5). In his lectures surrounding the founding of the first Waldorf school in Stuttgart, Steiner said:

Our times require it of us to completely relinquish the idea of handing on the content of our worldview to the children. The Catholic Child should have a Catholic religion teacher and be taught the Catholic doctrine; his religious exercises should be led by the Catholic religion teacher. The same holds good for the Protestant child. What must be brought about through the Waldorf schools we want to establish, is not to be found in the dissemination of a view of the world, but we want a new educational method, a new approach to teaching, a new didactic system sprouting from what we are able to bring. (Steiner, 1919)

While the current Waldorf syllabus for religious education – further highlighted in chapter 3.2 – aims to provide contents that cultivate and deepen ethical and social skills in children of all background, giving nourishment to the innate spirituality in

every child on a generic level (cf. [von Kügelgen, 2019](#)), this doesn't preclude the possibility of teaching blocks on specific Islamic contents for example for classes with Muslim children.

Celebrations

Celebrations represent an essential element of the Waldorf method and are profoundly conducive to children's development on a number of levels (cf. [Gläser, 2022](#)). Their merits and potential will be addressed in more detail in chapter 3.2.2. Since they are intended to evoke and cultivate a shared sense of joy and familiarity, appealing to the sensory not in a frivolous way but implying meaning, their implementation is most successful when both the aesthetic sense and spiritual sensibility of those involved is regarded. In my survey, one Waldorf parent stated she felt uncomfortable where school activities were evocative of pagan rituals. While the emphasis on the earth, its beauty and spirituality were perceived as conducive, neglecting to attribute it to Allah, the ultimate Creator of it all seemed to suggest worshipping the earth rather than Allah (P6).

With regards to Christmas, another participant didn't think the celebrations as such were problematic, but she would ensure it is clearly explained that for Muslims, what is celebrated is not Jesus'/Isa's birth but rather what he conveyed to humankind. It would be an opportunity for her personally to dedicate this time to reflect on Jesus, who is venerated by Muslims as a prophet, and on his message (P1).

Specific lesson block contents

Subjects such as sex education were considered positive in the survey, provided its child-appropriate implementation and care to ensure that Islamic values are not discredited (P1). Parents also stated they would appreciate being informed of the

contents in advance, so they could pick up the topic at home and complement it accordingly (P1, P2).

Pictorial representations

Another aspect that, although not explicitly mentioned in the survey, requires consideration is the handling of pictorial representations of elemental beings such as angels on the one hand, and of the prophets on the other. Islamically, neither may be portrayed or three-dimensionally depicted. Since any remotely adequate or accurate representation is impossible, its attempt would invariably depreciate the depicted. I found this aptly summarized in a recent reflection on the use of words, instead of pictures, to create images in education: "*The poverty of the pictures leads to an emptiness of the mental images.*" ([Wiechert, 2023](#)). Revisiting the merits of imaginal teaching, a method recommended by Steiner (cf. Chapter 2.1.3), serves to further illuminate this Islamic precept and points to the obvious alternative:

(...) When the word is used correctly, (...) then something special takes place in the children: as they listen, they form inner pictures, images of the story. This process of forming "mental images" is to a high degree an invisible but creative, active inner process. And we are faced with the great miracle: the imageless word creates images through listening. (...) ([Wiechert, 2023](#))

While using paint, felt and other materials for artistic expression holds in itself a panoply of benefits on various levels for the child, clearly the aim with regards to her spiritual development is not that she is able to reproduce a picture of what she has perceived from the unseen. Instead, the Waldorf method entails fostering in the children a sense of reverence for all beings in creation, which is considered a prerequisite for awakening a sense of responsibility (cf. [von Kügelgen, 2019](#)). Hence the question arises whether crafting a little gnome from felt to represent the spirits

of the forest, and placing it in the classroom for decoration, as is standard in most lower school grades, really does justice to the intention of imparting awe and veneration for these creatures of the unseen. Some would argue that it may rather induce the banalisation of those very encounters, especially in comparison with the blissfully awe-inspiring experiences children (and adults) can have just by being in nature.

3.1.2 Real issues

In January 2023, I had the opportunity together with others to address the topic of this thesis in the context of a workshop at the Waldoratorium, a Berlin-Brandenburg Waldorf school forum for sharing current pedagogic impulses (cf. [LAG, 2023](#)). The theme of the event was intersectionality and diversity sensitivity, the topic of my workshop was diversity sensitivity with regards to children and adolescents from practising Muslim families. In the course of our exchange, several probable reasons emerged as to why so few of them go to Waldorf schools. Firstly, in spite of Steiner's indicatory remarks to the contrary as cited in the previous chapter, teaching contents and celebrations in most local Waldorf schools are predominantly still shaped by a single religious denomination (Christian), which is not generally congruent with those of its students. Secondly, the topic of diversity regarding matters of gender and sexuality is now being widely introduced into Waldorf lesson planning, but so far largely to the exclusion of the Muslim perspective. In the UK especially, Muslims whose children attend mainstream schools have made the experience that this has taken place in a manner disregarding and sometimes implicitly denigrating Islamic spiritual practice, which has accordingly caused their apprehension. And thirdly, although far less severely than at mainstream schools (cf. [Yegane, 2023](#)), Muslim students have experienced patronizing and disparagement concerning their spiritual practice, also at Waldorf schools.

In preparation for the aforementioned workshop, I had asked several German, Muslim teenagers who had been visiting the same Waldorf setting since kindergarten, whether they had ever experienced that Islam-related matters were mentioned at school in a way they didn't feel comfortable with. Their replies in form of voice messages turned out to be intimate reports, detailed and very moving, conveying quite clearly how subtle and unwitting, yet far-reaching, discriminatory situations had occurred in an otherwise beloved and trusted setting. Some examples to illustrate this point, which I translated from German, follow below:

A ten-year-old girl tries out wearing a headscarf for the first time, which is commented on by her teacher in class („What's that you're wearing there?"), and again the next day („Why are you wearing that again now?"). In the girl's words, the teacher sounded „hurt" at that. Another girl of the same age is approached by the same teacher, asking her why she is not wearing a headscarf, which leaves the girl upset.

Since puberty, the first girl wears a headscarf at school every day, which has since been accepted by the class. When a new student, also a girl from a Muslim family, arrives in ripped jeans, with bare midriff and no headscarf, the first girl senses that her Islamic practice with regards to clothing is suddenly being questioned by the class. She is asked by one class mate whether she had „hammered her scarf on her head with nails". Most hurtful to her are her classmates' repeated questions whether she was being forced by her family to wear the scarf.

When an elementary school girl asks her about the colour of her hair, she doesn't get to reply: a teacher intervenes, telling the child not to ask, since the scarf is meant to hide the hair plus she can tell by looking at the eyebrows. Although the Muslim girl perceives that the teacher meant well, she feels annoyed since she would have preferred to respond to the child herself. She is left feeling „different" and „not normal".

Another example shared by the same girl: a mediocre translation of a verse from the Qur'an is discussed in class, dealing with the life arrangements of married couples and seemingly implying legitimation to constrain the woman. The girl finds herself confronted with her classmates' indignation and feels „cornered“. She feels as if her entire class now thinks she must be „insane“. Lacking the expertise to contextualize the verse there and then and to expound it for her classmates to understand, she still senses with certainty that something „is wrong“. At home, she looks up the verse in the Qur'an and finds that it goes on much further, and that its meaning is only complete and no longer one-sided by the end of the verse.

A Muslim, former student at the Waldorf school recounts that it used to bother him greatly whenever his teacher asked him to make statements regarding political matters where Islam or Muslims were involved. Although he expresses his sympathy for the teacher's interest, he still felt very uncomfortable being consulted as identification figure and „expert“ for complex and disturbing issues, especially since he tends to be introvert and sensitive by temperament. In that, he intensely felt the pressure of seemingly having to defend his life practice, and repeatedly made the experience that he does not have any perspective of value to offer to the teacher, whose opinion was already fixed. Looking back, he assumes things may have been different if there had been other Muslim students in his class.

Another Muslim, former student at the Waldorf school was deeply shaken and disillusioned when, on leaving the school prior to graduation, his former class teacher bode him farewell in a concerned manner, advising him to please not affiliate himself to a terrorist organisation.

A Muslim girl from seventh grade recounts an experience that stuck with her since grade one. Her classmate, also from a Muslim family, came to school wearing a headscarf one day when the class teacher, whom both girls loved dearly, „snarled“ at her, saying that she will have to „talk to her parents about this“ and that this was „really inappropriate now“. She still feels bad at the memory since she just stood by helplessly, seven years old at the time. Both girls have never since worn a headscarf at school.

A Muslim Waldorf school student was excluded from class against his will during Ramadan due to his appearing „lethargic“ to the teacher. Although this was consistent with his general disposition and the more so because he was going through puberty at the time, the college of teachers decided his exclusion. The result was a lasting breach of trust between the teachers and the parents of the student, whose younger siblings were at the time visiting the same school.

A lively exchange took place in the course of the workshop, during which several questions were formulated and addressed with regards to the circumstances Muslim students find themselves in at a Waldorf school. They are rendered here, essentially comprising all the concerns that also reflected in the survey for this thesis:

1. Is it acknowledged within the school that the development of their spiritual practice is an individual and sensitive process for Muslim (as for any other) students? Is their family's way of life indirectly questioned in class – which would inevitably interfere with this process?
2. With regards to this, how are Muslim students' needs met? For example, is room made available for students from the age of puberty, where they can perform their prayers during the winter months (when the days are shorter and prayer times accordingly in close succession, so that otherwise, they would be bound to miss their noon prayer)?
3. Are sensitive topics addressed in a mindful manner? Are students exposed to inconsiderate or derogatory comments about Allah, the Prophets, Adam and Eve, or other topics similarly meaningful to Muslims?
4. Do teachers possess sufficient basic knowledge about Islam to be able to act mindfully? What sources do they consult for this purpose?
5. If boundaries are overstepped during the lessons with regards to Islamic spiritual practice, are Muslim students (and parents) expected to put up with it? Or, can attempts be made to find alternatives beforehand - together, creatively?

Reflecting on the subject of sex education may further illustrate this point. While in itself regarded as a blessing and a form of prayer, sexual activity for practising Muslims is limited to marriage, namely to partners of the opposite sex. Is this aspect of Islamic spiritual practice taken into consideration when teaching this subject? Are students indirectly called upon to take a stand on the matter?

While these aspects undoubtedly add complexity to the challenge of lesson planning, they can hardly be skipped if the intention is indeed to ensure Waldorf schools as places where children from all backgrounds are recognized and accepted. Muslims in particular have had to deal sufficiently with the expectation to bracket their religious sensibilities in the public sphere (cf. [Amir-Moazami, 2022](#) , 1), even with regards to *"the most intimate domains of life, such as sexual and affective practices"* ([Hernández, 2016](#) , 72). Current discourse has addressed this in the context of integration policies, discerning in certain governmental initiatives *"the project of reshaping Muslim subjectivities"* ([Hernández, 2018](#), 205), but it naturally applies to practising Muslims of western European background in the same way. A particularly disturbing echo of this plays repeatedly in numerous present-day European and American tv productions, where any appealing Muslim character is at some point inevitably shown drinking alcohol or engaging with a girlfriend or boyfriend. Non-practising Muslims are thus effectively presented as role models, whereas those implementing basic Islamic practices such as establishing the five daily prayers within their respective time frame or avoiding physical intimacy outside marriage, are pegged as near-extremist. This tendency is reinforced by initiatives like the 'Registry for Confrontational Religious Expression' in Neukölln, planned by DeVi e. V. (Association for Democracy and Diversity): Actions considered to be 'confrontational expressions of religion' and thus possible signs of radicalization can thus include requests for a prayer room, wearing a headscarf and fasting. Besides denying that for young people in their time of identity formation, practicing

their faith can be an emancipatory element, the concept of 'confrontational religious expression' also labels viewpoints and behaviours that differ from the current mainstream as potentially dangerous (cf. [Le, 2023](#)). Hence it exemplifies the necessity for a power-critical examination of any formal "prevention of Islamist radicalization", as shown in a recent research report published by the German Federal Agency for Civic Education (Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, [Le, 2023](#)).

Returning to sex education, how can a teaching block then be designed in a way that conveys contents relevant to students of all backgrounds, without ostracizing any of them? Ideas that were collected in the context of our workshop included focusing more on the general question of functioning, fulfilling relationships and intimacy, rather than on the range of sex practices. Copious subjects lend themselves to further exploration of this field, such as learning about levels of communication and its impairment by trauma effects, and our nervous system as the interface between our body and our psyche ([König, 2019](#); [Schwartz, 2019](#)). Ample scope to build depth can also be retrieved by exploring the actual diversity of expressions of love across time and culture, beyond the purely physical dimension.

3.2 Moving forward

In view of these observations, we find several starting points for responding constructively to the status quo. While the according awareness and advancement varies greatly among Waldorf settings, the reflections consolidated here may offer to all of them some leads as to what can be done on the part of the teachers and the wider Waldorf community.

When asked to imagine a Waldorf school suitable for their children or grandchildren, participants in my survey expressed the wish for their children to be seen and welcomed also with their requirements, including those based on their Islamic way

of life (P1, P2, P5); that good communication with parents was ensured and that teachers had a sound understanding of Islam (P2, P3). Addressing the fear of anti-muslim-racism, they suggested accordingly sensible personnel decisions and adequate teacher training courses (P1). This is a valid consideration also with regards to external staff, as in the case of workshops or main lesson blocks taught by guest teachers. One Berlin based collective of sex pedagogues, sex therapists and social workers (PRISMA), to name a positive example, has been conducting holistic, Waldorf-inspired sex-education workshops in varying formats, depending on age group and topic, that were well received also by Muslim participants, who found their perspective was taken into consideration.

Not only with Muslim children in the school, but also in view of the understanding that the original Waldorf curriculum is fraught with Eurocentric narratives (cf. [Rawson, 2017](#)), it suggests itself to start drawing more on the wealth of artistic, scientific, philosophical and historical Islam-related sources and subjects for main lesson block planning. As pointed out in brochure no.14 of the series "Perspectives", published by the research centre of the Federation of German Waldorf Schools (Bund der Freien Waldorfschulen), diversity with regards to both cultural and spiritual background is to be considered a resource ([BdFW, 2022](#)) and an opportunity to gain newness and profundity in teaching. To this purpose, teachers may enrich their storytelling repertoires with gems like Attar's Conference of the Birds or the delightful stories of Mullah Nasruddin. Converging elements in traditional narratives like the life story of Francis of Assisi, which is the basis for an established Waldorf - main lesson block in class two, are obvious highlights to be savoured, such as his extensive, cordial encounter with the Egyptian Sultan al-Malik al-Kamil ([BdFW, 2022](#)).

Another exemplary topic relevant to lower, middle and upper school grades is the concept of [caravanserai](#) and exploring its historical manifestations. It holds starting

points for a range of subjects such as zoology, architecture, poetry, geography and climate, alternative models of economies and of social and political structures. Classic main lesson blocks such as that on bees and honey in class two can be enhanced by references where applicable - as in this case, where an entire verse relating to it can be found in surah an-Nahl (The Bee) in the Qur'an. Likewise, standard choices like Columbus in class seven as "the" example for exploring distant shores, may be reconsidered in favour of Ibn Battuta, a traveller rather than a conqueror.

Keeping an eye out for the crescent moon, which signifies the beginning of the new Islamic month; and for the slightly older children determining the times for the five daily prayers by observing the position of the sun, are simple yet meaningful ways of creating references to Muslim children's lives throughout the school year. And based on Steiner's indications regarding the merits and potential of second language teaching, there is no reason why Arabic shouldn't already be offered (P3), along with the opportunity for older children to venture into the art of calligraphy. Further ideas and inspiration for teachers can be found with the trailblazers introduced in chapter 3.2.2.

With regards to those parents who find the Waldorf educational method to suit their Islamic life practice, it is my hope that this paper encourages them to seek out fruitful encounters with other Waldorf parents and teachers, actively appreciating both the wealth they are offered and that which they themselves bring to the table. Ultimately, our own intentions and the according initiative and demeanour make all the difference, as shown by the example of five Muslim boys and girls at the German Waldorf school mentioned in chapter 3.1.2: During their camping - class trip in 7th grade at the time, they spontaneously used a vacant, large enough tent for praying in *jama'at*, meaning one of them leading the others in prayer. In this way, they supported each other in establishing all of the five daily prayers

while away from home, including the one before sunrise, which left an impression and was positively acknowledged by the rest of the class and the teachers.

3.2.1 Religious education

Some participants in my survey expressed their wish for Islamic religious education, or at least general religious education including Islamic content, to be offered at Waldorf schools (P3, P5), which had not been the case in their experience. However, essentially this is an element intrinsic to Waldorf education, although its implementation varies considerably depending on the setting. Steiner considered spirituality an essential human feature that brings with it a sense of religiosity (cf. [Willmann, 2014](#)), which I here understand as the disposition to seek connectedness with our origin and final destination, and to find expression for this connectedness. His concept of a generic religious education is aimed to stimulate and strengthen in students of any denomination the emotional and ethical capacities that are required for developing this disposition. Among these are the capacity for trust, wonder, reverence, obedience, humility and loving devotion, the willingness to take responsibility and the capacity for universal gratitude (cf. [Willmann, 2014](#)). To this purpose, Steiner established an independent religious education class in the first Waldorf school in 1919 in Stuttgart to provide for the students who did not attend religious instruction offered by the churches (cf. [von Kugelgen, 2019](#)).

In his research paper on religious education at Waldorf schools in a non-Christian context, Carlo Willmann outlines how this generic curriculum is implemented by means of pictorial teaching (see chapter 2.1.3) and adaptable contents (cf. [Willmann, 2014](#)). Pictorial teaching implies communicating contents in ways that speak to the whole person rather than just the mind, thus facilitating aesthetic-emotional experiences with the potential for deeper reflection (cf. [Willmann, 2014](#)). With re-

gards to religious education, this didactic method aims to encourage students' own pursuit of questions of meaning, ethics and their approach to existence, and to sensitize them for moments of connectedness with the Divine. The choice of contents should be based on students' spiritual traditions, bearing in mind any precepts.

Willmann points out the question if "religiousness" can actually exist on a general level, without being situated in a specific form of corresponding spiritual practice. He likens it to the human capacity for language, which remains undeveloped without any actual, specific language to apply it to. The Islamic term *fitrah* as mentioned in chapter 2 lends itself to further exploration of this aspect which, however, goes beyond the scope of this thesis. It can be said that the generic approach to religious education, intended to serve as an introduction to religion, not as religious instruction (cf. [Willmann, 2016](#)), certainly fulfils its purpose in view of today's diverse class compositions.

While the according syllabus, developed by the international board of Waldorf teachers for religious education, allows for even more flexibility than those of other subjects in order to fit lesson planning to local circumstances, it still provides useful guidelines, based on students' developmental phases (cf. [von Kügelgen, 2019](#)). At primary school level, central themes are the direct experiencing of the wisdom in nature, cherishing all creatures accordingly, and witnessing how all of existence is sustained and pervaded by God (Muslim children might at this stage already be familiar with some of the ninety-nine beautiful names that represent Allah's attributes as manifested in existence, as these are often recited in form of a chant well-liked by preschool children: Al-Muqet means the All-Sustaining, al-Lateef the All-Pervading). The teacher introduces and discusses fairy tales, songs and stories intended to nurture children's profound trust in life, reverence for the creative force that originated it, and their sense of embeddedness.

In middle school, stories from scripture and specifically of the people mentioned in there, form the basis for reflections on individual and intertwining fate. Students learn that dealing with mistakes and trials, weaknesses, sorrow and loss is part of being human, as is love, compassion and hope. Teachers use biographies of the prophets, saints and other religious leaders to this purpose – an immensely interesting and, at the same time, sensitive task. Ideally, teachers will by then have had a chance to glean ideas and relevant material from previous encounters and collaborations with their diverse students' families in the school context.

In upper school, students are meant to learn in more detail about the various religions and spiritual traditions, enabling them to respectfully establish what they have in common and where they differ, as well as their chronology and the circumstances from which they emerged. At that developmental stage, students also learn to recognize that their own lives are connected to that of all people and thus have meaning beyond their own immediate horizon, and that they are therefore called upon to apply themselves in the world as best they can on the basis of their knowledge gained (cf. [von Kugelgen, 2019](#)). However, many Waldorf schools today lack religious education classes in the upper school grades (cf. [Erziehungskunst, 2016](#)).

The independent religious education class is not intended to lead students to a specific creed or religious community, nor did Steiner want it to replace denominational religious education for those whose families followed an established spiritual practice. Rather, he acknowledged religion as the realm where the parental home had the most impact on the school, and that this had to be taken into account (cf. [Erziehungskunst, 2016](#)). Anthroposophy as such envisages spiritual practice without any denominational commitment. However, Steiner was very clear in his assertion that anthroposophy must not be taught at Waldorf schools. He had explicitly offered it to teachers as an applied philosophy, bringing mindfulness and

profundity to pedagogical practise. Since it doesn't call for any denominational commitment, it is available also to those who already have another established spiritual practice, as well as to those with no creed whatsoever. Two quotes from chapter 3 are repeated here for emphasis:

What must be brought about through the Waldorf schools we want to establish, is not to be found in the dissemination of a view of the world, but we want a new educational method, a new approach to teaching, a new didactic system sprouting from what we are able to bring. (Steiner, 1919)

You must realize that the Waldorf School or any other school which might spring from the anthroposophical movement, would never wish to teach its pupils anthroposophy in the form in which it exists today. This I should consider the very worst thing one could do. For anthroposophy in its present form is a subject for grownups (...) (Steiner, 1922)

3.2.2 Celebrations

Celebrations, as previously mentioned, are essential to Waldorf education. They can be seen as an intensified form of pictorial teaching in units spread over the year, involving the entire school organism including children's families, and thereby creating community. Their purpose beyond this is manifold: One is becoming aware of and attuning ourselves to the rhythms in nature around us, such as the lunar and solar cycles, the change of seasons and their qualities. In that, there is a reminder of our being part of creation, and an opportunity to reflect on the meaning of these phenomena - which Muslims are repeatedly called on to do in the Qur'an (see chapter 2.1.3). Steiner, besides drawing on traditional lore, seems to have been extraordinarily perceptive for the signs in nature and their meanings, and accordingly he assigned certain developmental images (cf. [Gläserer, 2022](#)) to

a number of then locally established, seasonal holidays. The theme of finding and nurturing the light within during times of darkness is one example, fighting “the dragon” in form of inner stagnation and destructive tendencies, another. Steiner observed and described (for Central European latitudes) how the different phases of the year each come with certain inward challenges, rousing in us tendencies that require balancing out (cf. [Spitalny, 2022](#)). Through our conscious striving for balance (Arabic: *mizan*), they can turn into thresholds for inner growth. Artistic and physical activities as part of the school festivals reflect this intention and offer opportunities for the children to joyfully face and master the respective challenges.

From the early years on, annual celebrations also convey and preserve a sense of safety and embeddedness. As the children grow and the festivals’ format gets adapted accordingly, they experience the familiar elements on a new level each year, perhaps each time more conscious of its deeper meaning. Annual celebrations can thus serve as landmarks for both the changes witnessed in nature and those within ourselves – something teachers and parents can share in, too (cf. [Gläser, 2022](#)).

The challenge that diversity within the community with regards to culture and/or spiritual practice poses in this context, can be considered as an opportunity:

The details of what we bring into those festivals come from our local community connections. We may be in a situation where the nativity story is appropriate as part of a midwinter celebration of light and hope in the darkness, or we may not. That will require sensitive conversations with our colleagues and parent communities. We may have to give up much-loved traditions, familiar stories, and old habits. That will create space for something fresh to come in. Rudolf Steiner was very clear that we would be creating new festivals (see *The Cycle of the Year*), and that words would need to change. Reference to Christ, he said, for example, might not be relevant in future times, but the spiritual meaning would be caught by other terms (see *The Universal Human*). ([Taplin, 2022](#), 10)

At classroom level, some suggest to simply include all the different holidays that children celebrate in their respective homes into the annual cycle ([BdFW, 2022](#)). While the expectation that children in class should participate in actual rituals from spiritual traditions other than their own must be considered problematic (see chapter 2.2), sharing foods, telling stories and playing games associated with festive days of various traditions can only be conducive to an atmosphere where every child feels appreciated and also comfortable in a diverse environment. However, *"Incorporating a new story, craft, or recipe into the rhythm of the day should not feel like an act of tokenism but a gesture of active and meaningful relationship"* ([Wilson, 2022](#), 14). Within the Waldorf community these days, there is increasing awareness of teachers' responsibility to create a sense of belonging for all the students in their class, as well as for their families, while maintaining the art of festival work that enables those deep, inner experiences for the children (cf. [Wilson, 2022](#)). One Muslim mother shared in my survey her impression of the Lantern Festival at her children's Waldorf school:

They would invite us to the festivals, the honouring of the seasons (...) it's the season of darkness, it's winter, the very long nights are coming, but (...) in the same way that we light up the dark with candles etc. (...), their theme was to look for the light within. And so (...) all the little ones had this big discussion about what the light within was about. (...) What I loved about it is that it was connecting the outward with the inward, so it was understanding that spirituality is not just this thing that happens when you sit on the prayer mat. It was - really understanding that the elements in the universe around us reflect who we are, what we're experiencing inwardly - that inner compass in a way - and that gives you that connection, it gives the child that connection. Using the wonder of the sun and the moon and the length of the days and how the different things will manifest in nature...! (...) That light, that we're so seeking outwardly - it's also inward! (P7, 86-109)

Further inspiration and concrete guidelines for a contemporary approach to creating celebrations that speak to a diverse body of students can be found in the 2022 spring issue of [Gateways](#), the newsletter of the Waldorf Early Childhood Association of North America.

3.2.3 Trailblazers

Recognizing the compatibility between the Waldorf method and Islamic life practice, a number of people within the last decades have ventured to explore, practise and refine its implementation for Muslim students. Anjum Mir from the Waldorf Early Childhood Association of North America (WECAN) in Los Angeles has had twenty years so far of gathering both challenging and immensely rewarding experiences in this field, some of which she kindly shared with me in a video call. Especially inspiring for me was her reply to my question how she dealt with the customary display of the Sistine Madonna in the year 1 classroom. While some teachers in an effort towards inclusivity now choose variations of the painting, with a black skinned Madonna and child instead of Raphael's white version, this still disregards the Muslim perspective on pictorial representations (see chapter 3.1.1). Looking for another way to transmit to the children that sense of joyful secureness, she crafted her own family's picture from felt for the classroom – which turned out wholly suited to the purpose, inviting the children to immerse themselves in its vibrant softness, and which also happens to include a father in the scene. Her reflections on the process of discerning core Waldorf elements from their traditional, often Eurocentric or Christian vessels – and then finding new ones to fit the children in her class, her own being and the time we live in, encourage and hold great value for those considering becoming Waldorf teachers themselves.

(...) It was out of freedom that I recognized that to invite my students and families to partake of the nourishment and guidance that I wanted to provide and to give them the inspiration to meet me, I had to extend a bridge built of symbols that were familiar to them and to invite them into a space full of stories and traditions that were familiar and made them feel at home. Once they felt like I was striving to know them, they made efforts to know me and my offerings. ([Mir, 2022](#), 7)

Mir, Anjum (2010). Felt Family [raw sheep wool]. Los Angeles, United States.

Regarding the sense of resonance Muslims can perceive when learning about the Waldorf method, Mir expressed that its epistemological foundation, Anthroposophy, served as a means for her to deepen her understanding of her own, Islamic spiritual tradition *"in the same way that a well-crafted pair of lenses defines and sharpens what we perceive in the world"* ([Mir, 2022](#), 5).

After years of Waldorf-inspired homeschooling, Hanan Sandercock from Wales, a practising Muslim for nearly 30 years, found the Cardiff Steiner kindergarten to be the right place for all her four children, and became part of the staff herself in 2014. Although she is quite familiar with some of the challenging issues addressed in previous chapters, her overall experience as a Muslim at the Waldorf setting in Cardiff has been and still is one of feeling welcomed and appreciated, as are her hand-crafted contributions, décor for Eid-day and other occasions.

While children's developing and learning in the context of a class community is a meaningful part of the Waldorf method, factors like private school fees and remote locations still prevent access for many, also Muslim parents. Those among them resorting to homeschooling have long been able to find inspiration and resources online, where other Muslims like Ashley May, an ethnographer in Los Angeles ([Waldorfy, 2020](#)) and Hana Khatib, avid homeschooler of four children, share their enthusiasm for the Waldorf approach, as well as a wealth of practical experience, tutorials and main lesson block ideas ([Pepper&Pine, 2024](#)).

In terms of physical Waldorf school settings in a Muslim context, the most long-standing example is certainly the Sekem school near Kairo, established in 1989 as part of a much larger, sustainable development initiative. At Sekem, certain elements such as the first line of the morning verse were slightly adapted to fit Islamic understanding: "The sun" was replaced with "Allah", reading: "Allah with loving light makes bright for me each day". The morning verse is always complemented by a recitation of Qur'an from the class teacher or, in the higher grades, the students (cf.

[Willmann, 2014](#), 85). As part of their weekly conference work, teachers practice communal *dhikr*, an Islamic form of contemplation and remembrance of Allah. Collectively reciting Allah's name "as-Sabur" ("the Most Patient") for example, helps teachers to align with that quality of patience in order to bring it to their work with the students (cf. [Willmann, 2014](#)). In 2017, a second setting dedicated to implementing the Waldorf approach was opened in Egypt, just outside Luxor. This school called "Hebet el-Nil" (gift of the Nile), observes religious holidays and events from both Islam and Christianity to ensure any children from Christian families don't feel left out. There is a particular affinity for eurythmy at this setting, which is considered to resemble elements of *sama'*, another form of *dhikr*, and to nurture children on both an emotional and a spiritual level.

When I came upon the homepage of the Waldorf school of Jordan in Amman, I was at first slightly startled by its style and tone: Not only did it seem so different from the familiar "Waldorf-style", which has a somewhat hippiesque, warm rainbow colour scheme and anthroposophic terminology. But also the way in which the setting's educational methods were presented – aimed to convey competence and excellence, emphasizing academics, assessment and international accreditation – rather made me think of a private school (which it is in any case) that would be favoured by highly educated, high-achieving parents with even higher academic expectations for their offspring, perhaps prioritizing measurable achievement over spiritual unfolding. Only towards the end of writing this thesis did I go back to take a closer look at it, as it resonated with something Hanan Sandercock had mentioned in our conversation. When I had asked why, in her view, there were only five Muslim families including her own at the setting in Cardiff, she told me it was because most Muslim families couldn't afford the school fees. But, she said, those who can would not consider sending their children because in their understanding, achievement shows primarily in exam results which, at Waldorf schools,

don't come into play until the upper grades. At that, I remembered the extensive, insightful commentary one of the participants made, preliminary to the questions in my survey (see appendix): She suggested that the common denominator for Muslims who don't consider Waldorf for their children is not primarily to be seen in their Muslim creed. But rather, it appears to be a (western-capitalist) culturally induced, somewhat undifferentiated affinity for everything considered modern, fast-acting and associated with progress and affluence, a tendency frequently found also among present-day Muslims in and from Arab countries, North Africa and Asia ([Baber, 2016](#)), as were the parents in Cardiff who decided against Waldorf. While it is by no means just parents from Arab and Asian countries who seem to be unaware of the established benefits of certain educational methods inherent to Waldorf, such as a later start in reading ([Schweinhart & Weikart, 1997](#); [Palmer, 2021](#); [Upstart, 2024](#)), the general emphasis on intellectual subjects along with the neglect of artistic, creative ones was also pointed out by another participant who had himself attended schools in Iraq, Syria and Yemen (P3). Considering the substantial artisan legacy of islamically shaped, refined cultures in large parts of the world, this brings up questions of why and how this apparent shift in Muslim thinking with regards to priorities in education has happened. Herein lies a topic for further research, to which one approach might be found in references to the impact colonization had on educational structures within Islamic communities:

Misogynism was internationalised, as Aisha Bewley, writer and translator of the Qur'an describes, by western colonial authorities who excluded women from teaching in mosques and assuming political roles in the Muslim societies they colonised. "The lens through which the West viewed Muslim women was already a distorted one – and once imposed or implanted among the Muslims, this viewpoint gradually became an established norm." **As the technologically and scientifically superior western culture impressed Muslim intellectuals, they grew more open to the values that these cultures brought with them.** ([Suleman & Rajbee, 2007](#)) (my emphasis)

At a time where it has become obvious that teachers can not know the contents that will be relevant for their students' future, current educational discourse focusses more on long term effects such as resilience, and substantiates teaching methods referred to as "Waldorf" accordingly ([Waldorf UK, 2024](#); [Flourish Project, 2024](#)). Child development expert and researcher Sue Palmer points out that children *"who are having the pressure for academic achievement put on them at an early age (...) – they're the ones who are going to lack resilience."* ([Palmer, 2018](#)). On being asked whether parents' ambitiousness for their children may have a downside, she comments:

Well, it's the child that needs to be wanting to learn. The problem I have with elitism, and this obsession with trying to become the best or reach the very top, means that automatically anybody who doesn't reach those heights is a loser. That of course is the basic mantra of marketing, you know, 'if you don't buy our product you're a loser', so what everyone is doing is buying into this marketing idea (...). ([Palmer, 2018](#))

Bearing all that in mind, it concludes that making Waldorf education more accessible to Muslim families may not only require accommodating Islam as a spiritual practice within the school organism, but also to *"meet the parents where they are with regards to their understanding of things"* (P1 comment, 63-64) such as academic achievement, assessment and international accreditation. This is what the board of the Waldorf school of Jordan appears to have recognized and skilfully implemented on their homepage, where parents are informed about how excellence – in a holistic sense at that – can be achieved by means of Waldorf methods. With regards to assessments, for example, the homepage reads:

Our goals for students are holistic, broad ranging, research based, and in line with Waldorf education's picture of child development. (...) To be truly effective, assessment of student progress must consist of more than just a set of standard exams. Genuine assessment should take a

360° view of each student using a variety of tools throughout their educational journey. (...) An appropriate way of assessing students in Grade 2 may not be useful in Grade 5, and vice versa. ([The Waldorf School of Jordan, 2024](#))

4 Conclusion

The principal appeal that lies in Waldorf education for Muslims is its holistic approach, which considers children's spiritual, physical and artistic development equally important to the development of their intellect. By taking children's formation of will explicitly into account, Waldorf teaching intends for them to become inwardly free beings, and nurtures their developing capacity for knowing and refining their own character. This includes fostering a sense of connectedness, purpose and responsibility in the world, as expressed in this verse composed by Rudolf Steiner, which is recited before class by grades 5–8 each morning:

I look into the world
wherein there shines the sun,
wherein there sparkle stars,
wherein the stones repose.
The plants, they live and grow,
the animals feel and live,
and humankind does give
a dwelling to the soul.
I look into the soul
that lives within my being;
the World Creator weaves
in sunlight and in soul-light
in world-space there without
and soul depths here within.
To Thee, Creator Spirit
I will now turn my heart
to ask that strength and blessing
for learning and for work
will ever grow within me.

Consistent with Islamic recommended practice, the Waldorf curriculum is essentially patterned on children's developmental phases in their sequence of seven-year-cycles. They are formulated as motifs and activities, not contents (cf. [Bransby and Rawson, 2023](#)), since rather than a vessel that must be filled with the greatest possible amount of information, the child is regarded as a seedling: The Waldorf teachers' task is to provide a safe and nourishing learning environment, at the best possible fit for each child - apart from that, teachers are to stand back and just witness their unfolding. This approach resonates with the Islamic teaching that children do not belong to their parents but are their *amanah*, (Arabic for: charge, ward) and ultimately have their own destiny (Arabic: *qadr*).

Besides the compatible aspects, there are also a number of obstacles for Muslim parents in sending their children to Waldorf schools. One is the fear that due to their developing Islamic life practice, expressed in their apparel, their common language use and their way of praying, their children might attract negative attention and experience deprecation at school. Given the regrettably awkward treatment of some Muslims at certain German Waldorf schools, these concerns are understandable, all the more so in view of local district initiatives such as the registry for "confrontational religious expression" in Berlin (cf. [Le, 2023](#)).

However, in focussing on the original intention of its founder, the Waldorf movement of today is increasingly geared to create a sense of belonging for students and families of all backgrounds, acknowledging diversity also with regards to their spiritual practices. As Rudolf Steiner intended for the Waldorf method to be adapted to any cultural and spiritual context, its flexibility in implementing the curriculum is really one of its great features, aiming to ensure contemporary relevance. While there are still considerable gaps and shortcomings in many settings when it comes to Islam-related teaching contents, this needn't remain so as vast room for creativity is left to the teacher, who is regarded as an artist of education. Accordingly, the qual-

ity of the actual teaching depends largely on this person, which is why sensitizing teachers to the lifeworlds of Muslim students should be addressed in teacher training, upskilling and the weekly teachers' conferences (cf. [Willmann, 2015](#); [Le, 2023](#)).

Another aspect to be considered in making Waldorf education more accessible for Muslims was found in the manner of interaction and exchange with students' families. Parents from cultural spheres where the current standard is to measure children's achievement typically in number grades based on exams and to give priority to cognitive contents, require to be met where they are in terms of their understanding of child development, wherever possible. This of course holds true irrespective of any religious background, but appears to be a relevant factor regarding Muslims from Asia and Arab countries in particular.

Finally, in entrusting their children to a suitable Waldorf setting, Muslim parents open up a treasure trove for their children, for themselves and the school community alike. As they discover the advantages of this educational approach, parents' active participation in class and school events such as crafts markets, celebrations, house building weekends and artistic performances naturally adds to the shape and colour of the entire school organism.

5 Appendix

These excerpts from my survey among Muslim parents provide some insights into both their expectations and their experiences with regards to Waldorf education. I have translated the answers of P1, P3, P4 and P5 as well as P1's commentary from German into English and added bold print in some places for emphasis.

5.1 Survey summary

Question 1: *Would you like for your children or grandchildren to attend a Steiner/Waldorf school?*

P1, P4, P5 and P7: yes; P2 and P6: maybe; P3: no

Question 2: *What about the Steiner/Waldorf educational approach do you find appealing - and what not?*

Appealing:

I have the feeling that it's more about observation - where is the child or the class at right now? And that's where they offer opportunities (...). It's not about "I've now learned something and now I'll be asked a question straight away, and now there's an F next to it because that was wrong" but simply about exploring. And I have the feeling that this is better for the psyche and the development (...) (P1, 130-136).

Having the same teacher for multiple years, fostering a child's individual interest (P2, 7-8).

What I like about the Waldorf concept, be it school or kindergarten, is the knowledge of spiritual faculties and the cultivation of these faculties, as well as the **knowledge of the Creator** (P4, 6-7).

I like the **rhythm according to the seasons**, the close attention and knowledge of the children's developmental stages, that God, the angels and the saints have a place in the lessons (P5, 5-6).

The teacher's personal, individual approach to each child, but also collaborative learning (e.g. theater projects, joint presentations), **fear-free learning** without the pressure of grades, but with a detailed, written discussion (I think dialog reports are great, too), the learning of extensive manual, artistic, musical and also intellectual skills, that children find out their very own qualities / abilities and become self-confident, socially competent adults (P5, 15-20).

I love that they put less academic focus on children at a young age, for example reading. I like how they encourage children to be creative and expressive. (...) I think honing in on a child's **imagination and creativity** is incredibly valuable, especially in this day and age as with the upraise of screens and social media our imaginations are severely impacted. Enhancing this imaginative spirit helps a child to think creatively and outside of the box and therefore not feel like they have to fit in to a particular mould that society elsewhere dictates to us. Also I believe a young child should learn through

play and exploration. So the delayed reading I think is also beneficial to the child (P6, 6-20).

Not everyone can afford Steiner for the whole stretch, but very often it helps some children that have educational trauma, and it helps just like therapy, so that they can **lose the fear of learning**. So some parents might not do the whole journey Steiner schooling. But it can be very beneficial to put your child there and do a couple of years. And in those couple of years, you know, the family will do whatever sacrifices they can to make it financially work. (P7, 34-39).

The spirituality - and that (...) will mean different things to different people. (...) The daily rhythms, and seasonal, of course, allow the children to **access their natural spirituality**. When you've got all these rigid structures, tables, lots of noise, lots of artificial stimulation, lots of stress - that creates a block. But when you've got this beautiful, safe rhythm that allows the child to feel very held and at peace - that allows them to access that inner voice. (...) They're accessing nature, which is really a connection with the divine. (...) There are all these sorts of philosophies - but ultimately, it is connecting with God.

And the other important part of Steiner education is the regulation of **the nervous system**, which happens with the daily rhythm (...) and the seasons (...). A lot of people say it's about the curiosity, the creativity, and I love those elements as well. (...) When we first started (...), it blew my mind what some of the six year olds could achieve with the beeswax crayons, and they all do this incredible kind of weaving.. there's a lot of woodwork, a lot of handicraft, and that **creativity lends itself to so much confidence**. And also - we are navigated by our nervous system. So, to have them at that age in these beautiful rhythms is such an extraordinary blessing. But also of course, that creative opening. They **create wild and wonderful things** and it blows your mind (...). (P7, 69-120).

Unappealing:

First name basis. That's the other thing. I am all for titles and respect. It's not the end of the world, I can see what they're trying to do. They're trying to create that familiarity between the teacher and the student, but certainly in the UK, teachers are on first name basis, and that's just something that I didn't like because I do still like to uphold that slight respect and reverence for elders (P7, 167-171).

I don't like the sometimes sect-like behavior of some educators, which doesn't allow them to question their positions (P4, 12-13).

I don't like the fact that the system is sometimes too rigid and that there are not so many concepts, e.g. for the gifted or disabled. The teaching framework is relatively strict (although much freer than in state schools). Christian

religion is too narrowly defined, other cultures and religions are hardly taken into account (in Germany). In view of a multicultural society, the system is too outdated (P5, 8-12).

When I went to view (...) the Steiner schools, a lot of them were quite filthy... not filthy, I mean, that's an exaggeration, but they were a little bit... you know how, sometimes, hippie things can get a bit scruffy (P7, 314-316).

Question 3: *Wherein lies the pedagogical value of Steiner/Waldorf schools, in your opinion?*

I believe that the learning concept is (...) more about exploration, investigation and the natural unfolding and development of learning. Not this reward and punishment approach that somehow reflects our society a bit. (...) You're supposed to get into this work-machinery and learn to obey and perform quickly, get paid for it - and then you end up in this hamster wheel - but you're prepared for it. (...) Above all, it also places value on the individual development and growth of the children (...) and I just think that's incredibly nice (P1, 145-165).

The fact that they work so much with their hands. (...) When I went to school in the Arab countries, for example in Iraq, Syria and Yemen, we didn't do so much with our hands, to be honest. And that's why, for example, I notice the difference compared to my German colleagues - they have more manual skills (...). We just did a lot with our heads. Mathematics, languages, the Qur'an, physics, things like that...sciences. (P3, 54-62).

In my opinion, the value of Waldorf schools lies in the opportunity for children to experience an unencumbered and non-competitive time at school and to build a strong sense of self-worth and a relationship with the Divine (P4, 16-18).

With my eldest, he didn't even know that letters ABC existed until he was seven years old. And there was a lot of anxiety around the approach that I was taking. But I was quite certain. Some people say: do you think it held him back? And he actually did phenomenally well. Mashallah, tabarakallah, when he did his entrance exams last year, he was also interviewed and got into one of the top schools in the UK. And when he was interviewed, the teacher actually said to me: congratulations on such a marvellous young man! And (...) people kept saying: ooh, he got in and did so well despite the fact that you did teach him later how to read and write, and you let him just do free play (...) when he was little - I actually hit reply to them. He did so well because of that approach, which was delayed formal learning, lots of time in the forest, focus on creativity before rigour, phonics and times tables and things like that (P7, 176-189).

Question 4: *Where do you see potential problems with regards to your religious life practice?*

When my son says „it's prayer time“ or „I feel like praying now“ (...) he then simply prays in the playground, just like that. (...) So, if he were to do that at the setting, I think it might offend. I have the feeling it wouldn't be alright. (...) so if a child now decides to pray in the Christian way somehow, I don't think the child would be stopped in the classroom. That's my fear.

I see problems, even if my son now says „bismillah“... he says „mashallah alayk“ a lot. (...) I'm afraid of Islamophobia and anti-muslim racism, that somehow, these things are not okay when he says them, because the others don't understand what he's saying, but that he also is not being asked: why are you saying that? And if someone says “thank God”, then of course that's completely fine. But if he says, “Alhamdulillah”, I think that it would be like this: “Oh no, why are you saying these weird things?” Instead of saying: “What does Alhamdulillah mean?” If he would say it means thank God, I think everyone would be happy again.

And I'm afraid that will slow him down in his development and discourage him; that he will realize that maybe he doesn't fit in at all, that he wants to fit in a bit in a group like that. I think it's quite normal at a certain point for children to look for a small clique and try to create harmony. And I think in a group, if everyone was saying alhamdulillah, alhamdulillah, subhanallah and things like that, then that would be completely normal. But I think that's where my concern lies a little bit.

At the kindergarten where I tried to enroll him it just said: “We have Christian guiding values” - which to a large extent also overlap with the Muslim guiding values, so, in principle, it's actually all one. If it's Christmas, for example – I don't think it's an issue, but then I would just go back in with my child and simply explain, and really occupy myself a lot with our prophet Jesus aleyhissalaam, but then say ok - we don't celebrate the birth. Instead, we celebrate the things that he wanted to convey to us and did convey to us, and what are these things? And I would just go back to that. But I don't think that's so dramatic.

I think it would be worse if he was stopped from praying and things like that. So I think that's where I see a bit of a problem.

(...) I don't think the theory of evolution is an issue either. When it comes to teaching sex education, I also think it's good, but of course it has to be presented in a way that's suitable for children and yes, it also has to be made clear that it's not about showing two fourteen-year-olds having sex. But (...) that I just know what's being said so that I can somehow adequately educate the rest at home and adapt it. As in... boyfriend - girlfriend: perhaps that's just normal in the culture we live in here, but in Muslim culture - God intended it

differently for us, and so on and so forth. (...) But I think the only thing I would find really worrying would be if he was stopped in his practice like that. (...)

So I always have the feeling that this Islamophobia has really reached the last cell of the German mentality, because everyone else is accompanied with a great deal of devotion and a great deal of, how shall we say, very reliable support. So, when I see a child (...) from a Hindu family, it's always emphasized that they shouldn't eat beef, or maybe no meat at all (...) and then it was also explained that there are certain festivals... these are the gods... and this is to be taken seriously, it's not something to make fun of... like that. And I have the feeling that this is respected in all religions - whether Buddhist or, I don't know, Jewish, but when it comes to Islam, you're allowed to belittle it. You're allowed to make jokes with references to groups that spread suffering and misery everywhere and that also call themselves Muslim, but to which all German, Muslim, Islamic bodies have distanced themselves. Yes, and that it's simply okay, when it comes to Islam, to not (...) justify it. Well, I feel that it may happen superficially, but not honestly and deeply. It has no substance. It's done because it's in the curriculum, but it's not honest. So when people say, "no - here, we let everyone keep their faith", that means we let everyone keep their faith except for the Muslims. Because they're "evil". And that's just so deeply ingrained (P1, 177-261)

That's why I don't like it - this Western view of the world, especially about Islam. (...) it indirectly gives you an impression or an idea in your head that Muslims are terrorists and things like that. I don't know how others see it, but I see it so clearly in the West that Muslims are viewed very negatively. And I don't want to give my children this feeling that they belong to a group that is always viewed negatively. (...)

I see a lot of problems in Germany - that, as I said, historical events are sometimes misinterpreted. For the most part, the Western view is mentioned. It is not a neutral, logical examination of the events. For the most part, in my opinion, Islam is not taught at all in Germany and, as I said, when it is, it is always negative, in a largely negative context. (P3, 25-76)

With a few exceptions, only a Christian form of school is taught. Other religions play little or no role. Unfortunately, no other religion education class is allowed, nor was there a general/interreligious education offered for all, which I find very dramatic and also quite a shame. I think this is also an exclusion criterion for many people who'd otherwise send their children to a Waldorf school, because they are afraid that their children will be indoctrinated with Christianity. Unfortunately, Islam has also been completely misrepresented in some lessons because the teachers don't have the knowledge. I think that teachers generally need interfaith training. (...)

In general, Waldorf schools lack an understanding of other religions and there is also very little interest in integrating or at least seeing and respecting

knowledge and other cultures, their religions and rites. This is not about the old cultures. It is not acceptable for exams or class trips to take place on the most important holidays of other religions. (P5, 23-38)

Some Waldorf activities can definitely have a pagan feel. (...) When there is an emphasis on the earth and its beauty and spirituality but without attributing all of it to Allah, the ultimate creator of all, it can sometimes come across as being attributed to something else. Worshiping the earth, rather than Allah. (P6, 23-28)

Actually, I would go further to say that I really think a lot of Muslims aren't appreciating how the Steiner schooling is more in alignment with our Deen than any other type of schooling, because all of these things we have in our tradition - the idea of the child just playing until seven is from our tradition, the ideas of the themes behind the celebration of the seasons (P7, 262-267).

Question 5: If you imagine a Steiner/Waldorf school suitable for your children or grandchildren, what would it be like?

I would be really happy if non-violent communication was really practiced in depth. So that it's really clear that there's no rewarding and punishing, that the children's needs are seen, that the parents are also properly informed, that it's about lightness and not strictness. And of course I would also be happy if everyone were really seen with all their important components - for us it's simply our religion: that life has an end and that another one follows, which is the one we ultimately work towards - that this is fostered in our children (...) (P1, 234-242).

Regarding anti-muslim-racism:

I would really like them to do sufficiently research-based courses, further training and so on, and perhaps also to filter and screen their staff accordingly, so that this really happens on a sincere level (P1, 261-263).

I would want to feel that there was an understanding of Islam, that they were able to pronounce my children's names, that there is an understanding of having a halal diet. The school would be inclusive to children from all backgrounds and religions, it would be a friendly and welcoming place. I'd also want to know how and at what age they teach about relationships (P2, 14-21).

That the Arabic language is offered alongside German. If my children do go to school in Germany, it is very important to me that they learn German as well as Arabic. Not just as an Arab, but also as a Muslim, in order to understand Qur'an, Hadith, Sunnah, Fiqh and Islamic contexts. (...) and Islamic education, that would be important to me (P3, 98-105)

I would like it to be Muslims with sound knowledge of the subject who teach the children Islam (P3, 78-80).

I would have liked to have had Islamic or at least general religious education for my children, but we were denied this at the Waldorf School (P5, 32-33).

There would have to be an intercultural calendar in every school so that the class teacher can see: ah, my Jewish children, my Muslim children etc. have their holidays then and then this year, and plan accordingly. (...) Even small gestures, like congratulating each other on the holidays and integrating the theme into the lesson would be very helpful and nice for a society like ours (...) I would like an intercultural/interreligious Waldorf school for my children/grandchildren, where they feel equally recognized as Muslims, and feel seen and respected with their religion (P5, 39-48).

It would be a friendly space, lots of freedom for the child but within reasonable boundaries which are clear. (...) Love and appreciation for nature and the earth and by extension Allah. Above all, wonderful teachers who look out for each child's wellbeing and nurture their likes and interests (P6, 31-37).

This particular school was really well kept, like a really lovely cottage you would want to stay in. It had lots of gorgeous natural light. Lots of wood, lots of wicker and (...) really nicely decorated. They bring in the seasons, the flowers or the foliage, and the kids do incredible work and it's displayed. It's just a place of beauty. And I think that having a place that's clean, that's got natural light and is a place of beauty is really, really important (P7, 316-321).

5.2 Comment (P1)

I have one more comment before we start on the first question, which I'll give you now and then I'll give you my feedback on the other questions.

So, your paper deals with the question of why children from practising Muslim families make up a conspicuously small proportion in Waldorf schools in Germany. Well, (...) I've been abroad for a good ten years now, I lived in Bangladesh for a while, then I was in New York, then I spent several months in Congo, I was in Kenya, in Namibia and then I spent another two years in Guinea, in West Africa so I've just been around a bit. I've also been to South Asia - more on vacation - in Nepal and India for several months. So I'm saying that I have seen some of the global south

with regards to Muslim countries. Nepal and India are not predominantly Muslim, but Bangladesh is, too. And then, I married into a Saudi family, so I also have a bit of exposure in that direction. And one thing I can say is that what other people regard as valuable and beautiful and of high quality is not what we in our German-socialized brains see as high quality, beautiful and desirable. If we just zoom in on toys, for example: a toy that is very colorful and perhaps flashes or makes noises and has a battery is much, much better in the eyes of these parents than a wooden toy that doesn't do anything. And of course that's because the people who like wooden toys know the science behind a child's learning and know how a child's brain works, and what happens when you just give them a wooden toy and what happens when you give them a colorful, flashing, music-making toy. And (...) I think it has simply become so established in German culture that we see the added value.

(...) The same would perhaps also apply to clothing and (...) to an environment, i.e. a playground that is as colorful as possible, where there is perhaps also a TV on the wall with a movie playing or YouTube with children's videos and music, where everything is rather made of plastic - parents perceive this as an entertaining and child-friendly environment, and the Waldorf concept is simply not that at all. And I think that's why there's no compartment for this educational approach in their minds. If they ever took notice of this (Waldorf) environment, then they would probably consider it super boring because there's nothing entertaining for their children.

My whole Saudi family, they always turn on the TV and say, look, that's a great video, he'll learn something too! And then I try to explain to them that children under three don't take anything from a video, that there is no scientifically proven added value for the child in watching a video, no matter what it's about. Of course, there is added value for the family and perhaps the caregiver. For example, I had a situation like this yesterday, I had to make an incredibly important phone call, there was no daycare because he was unwell and had to stay at home, and I had to turn

on a video to calm him down so that I could make this phone call. Of course, that had added value for me, but it didn't have any added value for him, which is something that changes from the age of four, five, six and upwards, I think, as far as media is concerned.

So, culturally, it's completely different. The other thing I discovered was in England, where I lived for about five and a half years, working as a midwife. Many of my clients longed for German eco-products for their babies: wool/silk clothing, pure new wool clothing, boiled wool, our soft hairbrushes for the babies... They love German products because everything is eco-certified, dye-free, toxin-free, tested. So that's what the English love. (...) And if, for example, you had to sell a Waldorf concept to parents, Muslim or non-Muslim, but from a culture that is simply very remote and different from German culture, then you would really have to organize a flyer that is probably also very colorful, and perhaps it should have a German seal of quality - because that is what many people know: Germany has great products, great technology etc. (...) Perhaps you would really have to meet the parents where they are with regards to their understanding of things, and then simply say look, that's why we don't have any plastic toys here, or (...) anything with batteries. (...) When it comes to the question of practising Muslim families, I do believe that there are differences. I don't think it's Islam. Culturally, most Muslims are simply shaped differently, even if they are the third generation here, perhaps from Turkey or somewhere else, I think that runs deep, like the understanding of what the added value is for children and how they learn best and what they like and so on.

And then another thought, with regards to being Muslim: When I say that the cultural background - or let's say foreground - weighs more heavily than religion, which we see that in everyday life and also locally, in the respective countries - I think there's another very clear difference whether I'm talking to Muslim sisters from Indonesia, from Senegal, from Sudan, from Guinea, from Brunei, from Saudi

Arabia, from Kuwait - they are also completely different because the cultural imprint is simply so strong. And of course we all have something in common, but I would say that the understanding of child development and how to support it, is completely different in all these groups. For example, when I look at Pakistan: I have met many people from Pakistan who were all beaten in their childhood, across the board. And prophetically, we know that beating and any form of violence against children is not acceptable in any way - we know that from Hadith and from the Qur'an. And yet, that happens. I think there is something disjointed (...). I have now seen that again in Saudi Arabia. I often find it very un-islamic how children are brought up. Islam actually indicates so much in terms of child rearing, which you also address in your work here. But it is not at the forefront of parents' minds. So when I think of poorer contexts, some of the parents simply have other concerns. Now in Saudi Arabia, parents' worries are of a different sort - poverty perhaps plays a somewhat subordinate role, but in my opinion the children are still not brought up in an Islamic way, i.e. according to Islamic standards and values, but simply shouted at all the time, bombarded with some kind of media. And yes, that is simply cultural, I think. And something like Waldorf simply has no added value at all for the parents.

5.3 Bibliography

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